

22RPT04 RFMicrowave2

D7: Final reports on the interlaboratory comparisons on (i) low-frequency electric field, (ii) low-frequency magnetic field and (iii) high-frequency electric field in an anechoic chamber

Organisation name of the lead participant for the deliverable: LeftRight

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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For further details about the RFMicrowave 2 project see the project website <https://rfmwii.cmi.gov.cz/>

1 Summary

Deliverable D7 contains analysis of the intercomparison for 4 electric and magnetic field probes that was performed within *Development of RF and Microwave Metrology Capability II* (22RPT04 RFMicrowave2) project. The probes were:

- Narda ELT-400, *B*-field measured between 0.03 kHz and 400 kHz,
- Narda HF-0191, *H*-field measured between 30 MHz and 1000 MHz ,
- Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300, *E*-field measured between 0.01 kHz and 30 kHz and
- ETS-Lindgren HI-6053, *E*-field measured between 0.01 GHz and 40 GHz.

Five participants were involved in the intercomparison:

- SIQ
- CMI
- IMBiH
- RISE
- TUBITAK

Each laboratory was encouraged to participate in as many measuring points as possible while they could use different field realizations (*e.g.*, parallel plate capacitor, Helmholtz coil, TEM cell, pyramidal cell, fully anechoic chamber).

Additionally, LeftRight was included in this intercomparison as a support for analysis. Moreover, LeftRight was also responsible for another intercomparison loop which included Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 and Narda ELT-400 probes and three external laboratories that were not included in RF&MW2 project.

The D7 deliverable contains the technical protocol (Chapter 2). In Chapter 3 the analysis is shown, for each probe one subchapter. The measurement report of each partner is attached after Chapter 3. Finally at the end of deliverable, the analysis of external intercomparison loop is also given.

2 Technical protocol

2.1 Introduction

Within the scope of the Project of *Development of RF and Microwave Metrology Capability II (22RPT04 RFMicrowave2)*, activity A3.3.3, it is planned to perform the intercomparison related to field probe calibration. According to protocol, at least the following probes should be included:

- LF magnetic field probe,
- LF electric field probe and
- HF electric field probe.

After discussion it was decided that the following probes are included in the intercomparison (details are given in Table 1):

- Magnetic field probe: Narda ELT-400 (10 Hz – 400 kHz), Fig. 1,
- Magnetic field probe: Narda HF-0191 (27 MHz – 1 GHz), Fig. 2
- Electric field probe: Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 (5 Hz – 32 kHz), Fig. 3,
- Electric field probe: ETS-Lindgren HI-6053 (10 MHz – 40 GHz), Fig. 4

The frequency list and recommended field levels are given in Tables 5-8. Each participating laboratory should decide which field realization will be used. Each participating laboratory should calibrate as many probes and as many frequency points as possible (preferably all), but it is also acceptable to perform just one measurement of interest (*e.g.*, *E*-field at 50 Hz with Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe). The probes will be provided by TÜBİTAK (Türkiye). TÜBİTAK will be also responsible for monitoring of the standard's performance during the circulation. The evaluation and reporting of the comparison results will be performed by LR and SIQ. The comparison will be carried out in accordance with the CCEM Guidelines for Planning, Organizing, Conducting and Reporting Key, Supplementary and Pilot Comparisons [1].

Fig. 1: Narda ELT-400 probe used for the intercomparison.

Fig. 2: Narda HF-0191 probe used for the intercomparison.

Fig. 3: Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe used for the intercomparison.

Fig. 4: ETS-Lindgren HI-6053 probe used for the intercomparison.

Table 1: General specifications of the probes that are used for intercomparison as travelling standard.

Manufacturer	Magnetic field		Electric field	
	Narda	Narda	Wandel & Goltermann	ETS-Lindgren
Model	ELT Probe 100 cm ²	HF-0191	EFA-300, BN 2245/90.31	HI-6053
s.n.	M-1859	A-0310	A-0074	00224858
fr. range	1 Hz – 400 kHz	27 MHz – 1 GHz	5 Hz – 32 kHz	10 MHz - 40 GHz
Monitor device	Narda	Narda	Wandel & Goltermann	/
model	ELT-400	NBM 550	EFA-300, BN 2245	/
s.n.	O-0450	B-1002	A-0098	/
fr. range	1 Hz – 400 kHz	100 kHz – 60 GHz	5 Hz – 32 kHz	/

2.2 Participant Laboratories

The coordinator for this comparison is TÜBİTAK (Türkiye). The contact details of the coordinator and the participating institutes with contact persons and their addresses are given in Tables 2 and 3, respectively. LR will be responsible for preparation of the intercomparison report while not actively participating in the intercomparison. Moreover, according to the project protocol, two companies from Slovenia that are not part of the RF&MW2 project (externals) will also participate the intercomparison. Their details will be added later. They will perform the calibration at SIQ.

Table 2: Contact details of the coordinator.

Coordinator: Türkiye Bilimsel ve Teknolojik Araştırma Kurumu / Ulusal Metroloji Enstitüsü (TÜBİTAK UME)
Mehmet Çınar and Çağlar Aslan mehmet.cinar@tubitak.gov.tr caclar.aslan@tubitak.gov.tr Tel: +90 262 679 5000

Table 3: A list of participating laboratories.

Country	Institute	Acronym	Shipping Address	Contact Person
TÜRKIYE	Türkiye Bilimsel ve Teknolojik Araştırma Kurumu / Ulusal Metroloji Enstitüsü	TÜBİTAK UME	TÜBİTAK Ulusal Metroloji Enstitüsü (UME) TÜBİTAK Gebze Yerleşkesi Barış Mah. Dr. Zeki Acar Cad. No:1 41470 Gebze-Kocaeli, TÜRKIYE	Mehmet ÇINAR mehmet.cinar@tubitak.gov.tr Tel: +90 262 679 5000
CZECH REPUBLIC	Cesky Metrologicky Institut	CMI	Cesky Metrologicky Institut Radiova 1136/3 CZ-10200 Praha 10 CZECH REPUBLIC	Tomáš PAVLICEK tomas.pavlicek@cmi.gov.cz Tel: +420 266 020 185
SWEDEN	Research Institutes of Sweden	RISE	Research Institutes of Sweden Brinellgatan 4 504 62 Borås Sweden	Mats CEDHEIM mats.cedheim@ri.se Tel: +46 10 516 60 86
SLOVENIA	Slovenski Institut za Kakovost in Meroslovje	SIQ	Slovenski Institut za Kakovost in Meroslovje (SIQ) Mašera-Spasičeva 10 SI-1000 Ljubljana SLOVENIA	Marko BERGINC marko.berginc@siq.si Tel: +386 1 4778 340
BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA	Institut za Mjeriteljstvo Bosne i Hercegovine	IMBIH	Institut za mjeriteljstvo Bosne i Hercegovine (IMBIH) Branilaca Sarajeva 25, 71000 Sarajevo, BOSNA IN HERCEGOVINA	Osman SIBONJIC osman.sibonjic@met.gov.ba Tel: + 387 33 568 923

2.3 Time Schedule

The time schedule for the comparison is given in the Table 4. The circulation of travelling standards will be organized as ring style. Each laboratory will have maximum three weeks to carry out the measurements (if possible, less). Any deviation in the agreed plan should be approved by the coordinator. Each laboratory will arrange the delivery of the equipment to the next participant in the schedule list (Table 4) after completing the measurements. The travelling standard should be checked for damage immediately after reception. In case of damage, all participant laboratories should be informed immediately.

Table 4. Circulation time schedule (IMBiH and two external companies will perform the measurements at SIQ).

Acronym of Institute	Country	Measurements	Transportation to next participant
TÜBİTAK UME	Türkiye	16.06.2025 - 27.06.2025	4.07.2025
SIQ & IMBiH & 2 companies	Slovenia	7.7.-25.7.2025	1.8.2025
RISE	Sweden	4.8.-22.8.2025	29.8.2025
CMI	Czech Republic	1.9.-19.9.2025	26.9.2025
SIQ	Slovenia	/	3.10.2025
TÜBİTAK UME	Türkiye	6.10.-17.10.2025	end

2.4 Transport Case

The travelling standard (and miscellaneous equipment if any) will travel in a well-protected package whose dimensions are approximately (100 cm length × 100 cm width × 78 cm height) and a weight, including the travelling standards, of approximately 50 kg. The transport case can be easily opened for customs inspection. The content of the transport case is:

- Magnetic field probe: Narda ELT-400 (10 Hz – 400 kHz)
- Magnetic field probe: Narda HF-0191 (27 MHz – 1 GHz)
- Field Monitor for HF-0191: Narda NBM-550 (DC-90 GHz)
- Field Monitor/Analyser: Wandel & Goltermann EFA300 (5 Hz-32 kHz)
- Electric field probe: Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 (5 Hz – 32 kHz)
- Electric field probe: ETS-Lindgren HI-6053 (10 MHz – 40 GHz)
- Accessories (Fiber cables, Flash memory, Fiber to USB converter etc.)

2.5 Transportation of Travelling Standard

The comparison will be organised in one ring loop. Each participant laboratory is responsible for the transportation of the travelling standard to the next laboratory. The cost of transportation will be paid by the laboratory which sends the travelling standard. TÜBİTAK UME will start the intercomparison. After completing the measurements, TÜBİTAK UME will send the standard to SIQ where SIQ, IMBiH and two external commercial companies will perform the calibration. SIQ will then send the standards to RISE, and RISE will send the standards to CMI. After completing the measurements, CMI will send the standards to SIQ who will return them to TÜBİTAK UME (*i.e.*, the same institute from EU should receive and return the standards to simplify import/export procedures). Finally, TÜBİTAK UME will repeat the measurements to confirm the stability of the standards. Each participant is responsible for the transportation expenses to the next participant laboratory in the list. The estimated cost of the travelling standards (for carrier company which include also transportation insurance covering any damage caused to the equipment) is 50.000€. After arrival in the participant's laboratory, the standard (and accompanying instrumentation if any) should be checked and allowed to stabilise in a temperature and, if possible, humidity-controlled room for at least one day before use. Each participant has maximum three weeks to perform the measurement (if possible, less) and one week to allow transportation to the preceding participant in the list. In case of any damage or

malfunction of the travelling standard, the comparison will be carried out after the travelling standard is repaired.

Each participant laboratory is responsible for costs for the transportation expenses to the following laboratory, measurements as well as any damage that may occur within its country. The overall costs for the organisation of the comparison are covered by the coordinator. Coordinator has no insurance for any loss or damage of the travelling standard, except for the insurance related to the delivery to the first participant in the list (first transportation of the standards).

2.6 Measurement Quantities and Points

For each probe, a frequency dependent calibration factor CF should be calibrated, Eq. 1, where CF denotes the calibration factor that is the quantity for the intercomparison, B_x , H_x and E_x are the magnetic flux density, magnetic field strength and electric field strength, respectively, that are shown by the device. The B_s , H_s and E_s are calculable (*i.e.*, real) magnetic flux density, magnetic field strength and electric field strength.

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_s &= CF \cdot B_x \\
 H_s &= CF \cdot H_x \\
 E_s &= CF \cdot E_x
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

The CF has been chosen because different partners will likely perform the calibration at different field levels, therefore it would be difficult to compare different results. Additional important details about the intercomparison are gathered below:

- The CF and corresponding uncertainty (extended uncertainty with coverage factor 2) should be expressed in dB form.
- The frequency points and the recommended levels for each probe where the calibration should be performed are shown in Tables 5-8. Nevertheless, the calibration levels should be given, especially if the calibration was not performed at the recommended levels.
- The following settings should be chosen on all probes: **Freq Corr Off**, reading: **Actual**, **E_{TOT} or H_{TOT} (B_{TOT}) reading**.
- Each laboratory can choose the most appropriate field realization which can be also different for the same probe. However, it is strongly encouraged that the fully anechoic chamber and a horn antenna are used for calibration of the ETS-Lindgren HI-6053 E -field probe in the 500 MHz -40 GHz frequency range.
- Some probes show separate value for different orientations (x , y or z) but for the intercomparison **only a cumulative (total) field should be used**. The orientation for each probe should be as given in Figs. 5–8 (*i.e.*, most of the field is detected by the axis as defined in the Figs. 5–8).

In addition, the environmental conditions during the calibration (temperature, relative humidity) should be also measured. However, no correction will be applied for the ambient temperature and relative humidity.

Table 5: Frequency list and levels for Narda ELT-400 probe. Other settings should be **range: 320 μ T-Low, det: RMS, low-cut: 10 Hz, Field strength mode.**

f (kHz)	B_{ref} (μ T)
0.03	10
0.055	10
0.1	10
1	10
3	10
5	10
10	10
50	3
100	3
200	3
300	3
400	3

Table 6. Frequency list and levels for Narda HF-0191 probe. **Apply correction frequency: OFF**

f (MHz)	H_{ref} (A/m)
30	0.150
50	0.150
70	0.150
100	0.150
200	0.150
300	0.150
400	0.150
500	0.050
600	0.050
700	0.100
800	0.100
900	0.100
1000	0.100

Table 7: Frequency list and levels for **Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300** probe. Other settings should be **Measurement mode: Field strength, Range: Auto, Filter: 5 Hz – 32 kHz, Detection: RMS, Display mode: Live, Channel: Isotropic**

f (kHz)	E_{ref} (V/m)
0.01	50
0.02	50
0.02	500
0.05	100
0.05	1000
0.05	2000
0.1	50
0.4	50
1	50
1	1000
5	50
7	50
10	50
10	1000
15	50
20	50
23	50
25	50
27	50
30	50
30	500

Table 8: Frequency list and levels for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053 probe.

f (GHz)	E_{ref} (V/m)
0.01	20
0.03	20
0.05	20
0.07	20
0.1	20
0.2	20
0.3	20
0.5	20
0.7	20
0.9	20
1	20
1.5	20
2	20
2.45	20
3	20
4	20
5	20
6	20
7	20
8	20
9	20
13	20
18	20
20	20
25	20
27	20
30	20
35	20
40	20

Fig. 5: Orientation of the Narda ELT-400 probe in the magnetic field (Display shall be pointing up)

Fig. 6: Orientation of the Narda HF-0191 probe in the magnetic field

Fig. 7: Orientation of the Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe in the electric field

Fig. 8: Orientation of the ETS-Lindgren HI-6053 probe in the E -field

2.7 Measurement Instructions

Precautions

- In order to minimize the contribution of measurement interface software, NMIs should use the same PC interface software. The interfaces in the shipped versions will be used in the measurements of the HF0191 and HI-6053 devices. ELT 400 and EFA 300 devices are shipped with their monitors, no PC interface is needed during measurements. PC interface software for the HF0191(NBM-500) magnetic field probe and the HI-6053 model electrical field probe are shipped in a Flash Memory disk.
- Avoid extreme temperature, humidity or pressure changes as well as violent impacts.
- Traveling standards should be stored in the laboratory conditions for at least one day before starting the measurements so the temperature and humidity condition are stabilized.
- The ambient temperature and relative humidity must be measured. No corrections will be performed for temperature and humidity effects. The ambient temperature and relative humidity should be included in the report. Preferably, the measurements should be performed under the following environmental conditions:
 - temperature: $(23 \pm 2) ^\circ\text{C}$
 - relative humidity: $(50 \pm 20) \%$

2.8 Reporting

Each participant shall send the following files by e-mail to LR and SIQ within 30 days of completing the measurements:

- **Excel template file** containing measurement results and uncertainty estimates (see Annex A),
- **details of the participating laboratory,**
- **date of measurements,**

- **environmental conditions** (temperature, relative humidity),
- **nominal value of the fields** (B_s , H_s or E_s)
- **detailed description of measurement method and setup** used for attenuation measurements,
- **measurement results** (according to the Annex A format),
- **measurement standards** (and software) used in the comparison measurements,
- **traceability scheme** (if the traceability to SI is provided by another NMI, provide the name of the NMI to identify possible sources of correlation),
- **measurement uncertainty budget** where all (or at least the most relevant) contributions are listed and its combination briefly described (measurement uncertainty must be calculated according to [2] for a confidence level of 95% and according to the format given in Annex A.).

2.9 Final Report of the Comparison

LR and SIQ are responsible to prepare the intercomparison report. The Draft A version of the intercomparison report will be issued within one month after reception of the reports from all participants. Draft A Report will be sent to participants for discussion, amendment if applicable, and eventually for approval. The participants will have two weeks to send their comments about Draft Report A. After all potential amendments have been considered, and after final approval by all participants, Draft Report A will become the Final Report.

The comparison reference value, CRV , is calculated separately for each measured value (*i.e.*, each probe and each frequency). The CRV is considered as an estimation of the measurand according to the measurements provided by the participating laboratories. This estimation, y , is determined as a weighted mean of the provided results where the weights are the inverse values of the squares of the associated standard uncertainties. However, that cannot be applied in case where some of the measurements are not consistent with the others. The procedure is implemented in five steps:

1. **Comparison reference value $CRV(y)$** , using the inverse values of the squares of the uncertainties as the weights is determined using Eq. 2.

$$y = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i \cdot u^{-2}(x_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^N u^{-2}(x_i)} \quad (2)$$

2. **Standard uncertainty of CRV , $u(y)$** , is calculated using (3).

$$u(y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N u^{-2}(x_i)}} \quad (3)$$

3. **Consistency of results:** A χ^2 test is applied to carry out an overall consistency check of the results obtained (*i.e.*, if all results can be regarded to belong to the same statistical ensemble). For each measurement, the observed chi-squared value χ_{obs}^2 is determined using Eq. 4. The number of degrees of freedom is $\nu=N-1$ for N results. The consistency check is considered failed if Eq. 5 is satisfied where Pr denotes *probability of*. If the χ^2 test fails, then the laboratory with the largest $|d_i|$ value (see below for definition) is excluded from the

determination of the *CRV*, and the consistency check is repeated. The process is then repeated as needed.

$$\chi_{obs}^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{(x_i - y)^2}{u^2(x_i)} \quad (4)$$

$$\Pr\{\chi^2(\nu) > \chi_{obs}^2\} < 5\% \quad (5)$$

4. **Exclusion of incompatible results:** Compatibility index, d_i , is defined as the ratio between the difference from the reference value and the standard uncertainty, Eq. 6. The compatibility index $|d_i|$ describes the deviation from the *CRV* in relation to the calculated standard uncertainty of the deviation. The standard uncertainties of the differences corresponding to those laboratories whose results have not been considered in the reference value calculation are obtained by applying Eq. 7, since now the values are not correlated.

$$d_i = \frac{\Delta x_i}{u(\Delta x_i)} = \frac{x_i - y}{\sqrt{u^2(x_i) - u^2(y)}} \quad (6)$$

$$u^2(\Delta x_i) = u^2(x_i) + u^2(y) \quad (7)$$

5. **Degree of equivalence (DoE):** In each case, the degree of equivalence of laboratory i with the *CRV* will be determined as the pair of values for the deviation from the *CRV* and the uncertainty of this deviation $[\Delta x_i, u(\Delta x_i)]$ according to Eq. 8, where $u(\Delta x_i)$ is obtained by applying Eq. 9.

$$E_n = \frac{\Delta x_i}{U(\Delta x_i)}$$

$$\Delta x_i = x_i - y \quad (8)$$

$$U(\Delta x_i) = 2 \cdot u(\Delta x_i)$$

$$u^2(\Delta x_i) = u^2(x_i) - u^2(y) \quad (9)$$

Note 1: The factor 2 in Eq. 8 indicates a coverage factor of 95% corresponding to a Gaussian distribution function.

Note 2: Eq. 9 establishes a difference of two variances as consequence of the mutual dependence (*i.e.*, correlation) between x_i and *CRV*.

2.10 References

- [1] *CCEM Guidelines for Planning, Organizing, Conducting and Reporting Key, Supplementary and Pilot Comparisons*, 2007
http://www.bipm.org/utis/common/pdf/CC/CCEM/ccem_guidelines.pdf
- [2] *Evaluation of measurement data – Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM)*, JCGM 100:2008, First edition, September 2008 (available on the BIPM website:
http://www.bipm.org/utis/common/documents/jcgm/JCGM_100_2008_E.pdf
- [3] *UNE-EN ISO/IEC 17043:2010: Conformity assessment — General requirements for proficiency testing*, International Standardization Organization, 2010
- [4] *International Standard ISO 13528: Statistical Methods for Use in Proficiency Testing by Interlaboratory Comparison*. Reference number ISO 13528:2015€
- [5] *IEEE 287-2007, IEEE Standard for Precision Coaxial Connectors (DC to 110 GHz)*, 2007

2.11 ANNEX A, Participant report

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION

Laboratory Name:	
Name of contact person:	
Telephone number:	
E-mail:	
Address:	

OTHER DATA

- Temperature: (\pm) °C
- Relative Humidity: (\pm) %
- Nominal value of the fields (B_s or E_s)
- Measurement date:

STANDARDS USED FOR MEASUREMENT

Instrument Name	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial Number	Traceability

DESCRIPTION OF MEASUREMENT METHOD

...
...

DESCRIPTION OF TRACEABILITY

...
...

MEASUREMENT RESULTS

Narda ELT-400		
f (kHz)	Measured CF (/)	UNC of CF (CL = 95 %) (/)
0.03		
0.055		
...		
...		
300		
400		

Narda HF-0191		
f (MHz)	Measured CF (/)	UNC of CF (CL = 95 %) (/)
30		
50		
...		
...		
900		
1000		

Narda EFA-300		
f (kHz)	Measured CF (/)	UNC of CF (CL = 95 %) (/)
0.01		
0.02		
...		
...		
30		
30		

ETS-Lindgren HI-6053		
f (GHz)	Measured CF (/)	UNC of CF (CL = 95 %) (/)
0.01		
0.03		
...		
...		
35		
40		

UNCERTAINTY BUDGET EXAMPLE FOR EACH FIELD REALIZATION

Definition of contribution	Expected Value x_i	Standard Uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Distribution Function	Sensitivity Coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
Measured Value	Combined Uncertainty				
	Expanded Uncertainty (CL = 95%)				

3 Analysis of results

3.1 Probe ELT-400

The measured calibration factors (CF) from SIQ, RISE, TUBITAK; CMI and IMBiH are gathered in Table 9.

Table 9: The results measured by the partners. All uncertainties have normal distribution with $k=1$.

$Bref$	f	SIQ		RISE		TUBITAK		CMI		IMBiH	
		CF	N	CF	N	CF	N	CF	N	CF	N
$[\mu T]$	$[kHz]$	$[V]$	$[V]$	$[V]$	$[V]$	$[V]$	$[V]$	$[V]$	$[V]$	$[V]$	$[V]$
10	0,03	1,02	0,01	/	/	/	/	1,04	0,01	/	/
10	0,055	1,01	0,01	/	/	/	/	1,02	0,01	/	/
10	0,1	1,01	0,01	/	/	/	/	1,02	0,01	/	/
10	1	1,01	0,01	/	/	/	/	1,02	0,01	/	/
10	3	1,01	0,01	/	/	/	/	1,02	0,01	/	/
10	5	1,01	0,01	/	/	/	/	1,02	0,01	/	/
10	10	1,01	0,01	/	/	/	/	1,02	0,01	/	/
3	50	/	/	/	/	/	/	1,02	0,02	/	/
3	100	/	/	/	/	/	/	1,01	0,02	/	/
3	200	/	/	/	/	/	/	1,01	0,02	/	/
3	300	/	/	/	/	/	/	1,03	0,02	/	/
3	400	/	/	/	/	/	/	1,39	0,03	/	/

Afterwards, the weighed mean of CF and standard uncertainty were calculated using Eqs. 10 and 10, respectively. The results are shown in Tables 10 and 11.

$$y = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i u^{-2}(x_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^N u^{-2}(x_i)} \quad (10)$$

$$u(y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N u^{-2}(x_i)}} \quad (11)$$

Table 10: The weighed mean of CF and corresponding standard uncertainty of all results. Note that above 10 kHz only the results from CMI were available.

B_{ref} [μT]	f [kHz]	CF_{wm} [l]	N [l]
10	0,03	1,03	0,01
10	0,055	1,02	0,01
10	0,1	1,01	0,01
10	1	1,01	0,01
10	3	1,01	0,01
10	5	1,01	0,01
10	10	1,01	0,01
3	50	1,02	0,02
3	100	1,01	0,02
3	200	1,01	0,02
3	300	1,03	0,02
3	400	1,39	0,03

Afterwards, the consistency of the results χ_{obs} was calculated using Eq. 12. Afterwards, the *Chi-test* has been performed using the CHIDIST function in Excel. The consistency check is considered fails if Eq. 13 is satisfied. In our case the minimum value that was observed equals to 0.33 therefore no result (laboratory) needs to be excluded from the calculation. Finally, the degree of equivalence E_n has been calculated for each participating laboratory using Eq. 14. The results are gathered in Table 20. The E_n value should be within $-1.0 < E_n < +1.0$ interval. The maximal absolute value for E_n for SIQ and CMI are 0.48.

$$\chi_{obs}^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{(x_i - y)^2}{u^2(x_i)} \quad (12)$$

$$\Pr\{\chi^2(v) > \chi_{obs}^2\} < 5\% \quad (13)$$

$$E_n = \frac{\Delta x_i}{U(\Delta x_i)}$$

$$\Delta x_i = x_i - y$$

$$U(\Delta x_i) = 2 \cdot u(\Delta x_i)$$

$$u^2(\Delta x_i) = u^2(x_i) - u^2(y) \quad (14)$$

Finally, the *Degrees of equivalence (DoE)* and corresponding uncertainties have been calculated for each participating laboratory using Eq. 14. The E_n , Δx_i with corresponding uncertainty U_i , d_i and χ_{obs} are gathered in Tables 11-14. Additionally, the results are shown in Figs. 9-15 for each measured point.

Table 11: The Degree of Equivalence E_n .

<i>Bref</i>	<i>f</i>	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CMI	IMBiH
<i>T</i>	[kHz]	E_n	E_n	E_n	E_n	E_n
		[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
10	0,03	-0,34	/	/	0,34	/
10	0,055	-0,30	/	/	0,30	/
10	0,1	-0,31	/	/	0,31	/
10	1	-0,29	/	/	0,29	/
10	3	-0,30	/	/	0,30	/
10	5	-0,33	/	/	0,33	/
10	10	-0,48	/	/	0,48	/
3	50	/	/	/	/	/
3	100	/	/	/	/	/
3	200	/	/	/	/	/
3	300	/	/	/	/	/
3	400	/	/	/	/	/

Table 12: The x_i and corresponding uncertainty U_i .

<i>Bref</i>	<i>f</i>	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CMI	IMBiH	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CMI	IMBiH
<i>T</i>	[kHz]	Δx_i	Δx_i	Δx_i	Δx_i	Δx_i	U_i	U_i	U_i	U_i	U_i
		[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
10	0,03	-0,005	0	0	0,007	0	0,015	0	0	0,021	0
10	0,055	-0,004	0	0	0,006	0	0,015	0	0	0,021	0
10	0,1	-0,004	0	0	0,006	0	0,014	0	0	0,021	0
10	1	-0,004	0	0	0,006	0	0,014	0	0	0,021	0
10	3	-0,004	0	0	0,006	0	0,014	0	0	0,021	0
10	5	-0,005	0	0	0,007	0	0,014	0	0	0,021	0
10	10	-0,007	0	0	0,010	0	0,014	0	0	0,021	0
3	50	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	200	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	300	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	400	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 13: The d_i parameter (exclusion of incompatible results)

<i>Bref</i>	<i>f</i>	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CMI	IMBiH
<i>T</i>	[kHz]	d_i	d_i	d_i	d_i	d_i
		[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
10	0,03	-0,69	/	/	0,69	/
10	0,055	-0,61	/	/	0,61	/
10	0,1	-0,61	/	/	0,61	/
10	1	-0,57	/	/	0,57	/
10	3	-0,61	/	/	0,61	/
10	5	-0,67	/	/	0,67	/
10	10	-0,97	/	/	0,97	/
3	50	/	/	/	/	/
3	100	/	/	/	/	/
3	200	/	/	/	/	/
3	300	/	/	/	/	/
3	400	/	/	/	/	/

Table 14: Consistency of results

<i>Bref</i> [μ T]	<i>f</i> [kHz]	x_{obs}^2 [/]	<i>N</i> [/]	<i>chidist</i> [/]
10	0,03	0,48	2	0,49
10	0,055	0,37	2	0,54
10	0,1	0,38	2	0,54
10	1	0,33	2	0,57
10	3	0,37	2	0,54
10	5	0,44	2	0,50
10	10	0,94	2	0,33
3	50	0	1	/
3	100	0	1	/
3	200	0	1	/
3	300	0	1	/
3	400	0	1	/

Fig. 9: Degrees of equivalence for Narda ELT-400 probe at 10 μ T and 0.03 kHz.

Fig. 10: Degrees of equivalence for Narda ELT-400 probe at 10 μT and 0.055 kHz.

Fig. 11: Degrees of equivalence for Narda ELT-400 probe at 10 μT and 0.1 kHz.

Fig. 12: Degrees of equivalence for Narda ELT-400 probe at 10 μ T and 1 kHz.

Fig. 13: Degrees of equivalence for Narda ELT-400 probe at 10 μ T and 3 kHz.

Fig. 14: Degrees of equivalence for Narda ELT-400 probe at 10 μT and 5 kHz.

Fig. 15: Degrees of equivalence for Narda ELT-400 probe at 10 μT and 10 kHz.

Unfortunately, only two laboratories participated in this intercomparison in a frequency range 30 Hz – 10 kHz while above 10 kHz only CMI was able to perform the measurements. However, there is a good agreement between both laboratories ($\chi_i > 0.05$, Table 14) in this frequency range therefore no exclusion of the results is necessary.

3.2 Probe HF-0191

The same analysis procedure has been performed also for Narda HF-0191 probe. The results measure by the partner are shown in Table 15.

Table 15: The results measured by the partners. All uncertainties have normal distribution with $k=1$.

Href	f	SIQ		RISE		TUBITAK		CMI		IMBiH	
		CF	N	CF	N	CF	N	CF	N	CF	N
[A/m]	[MHz]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
0,15	30	1,11	0,03	1,00	0,02	1,06	0,03	1,10	0,03	/	/
0,15	50	0,96	0,03	0,81	0,02	0,92	0,02	0,94	0,03	/	/
0,15	70	0,94	0,03	0,84	0,02	0,94	0,02	0,95	0,03	/	/
0,15	100	0,94	0,03	/	/	0,97	0,02	0,98	0,03	/	/
0,15	200	0,98	0,03	/	/	0,97	0,02	1,02	0,03	/	/
0,15	300	1,00	0,06	/	/	1,00	0,02	1,06	0,06	/	/
0,15	400	1,00	0,06	/	/	1,00	0,02	1,03	0,05	/	/
0,05	500	0,96	0,06	/	/	0,96	0,04	1,03	0,06	/	/
0,05	600	0,93	0,05	/	/	0,99	0,04	0,99	0,05	/	/
0,1	700	0,90	0,05	/	/	0,96	0,04	0,96	0,05	/	/
0,1	800	0,93	0,05	/	/	0,95	0,04	1,03	0,05	/	/
0,1	900	/	/	/	/	0,95	0,04	0,90	0,05	/	/
0,1	1000	/	/	/	/	0,95	0,04	0,99	0,05	/	/

The weighed mean of CF with standard uncertainty, *Degrees of Equivalence* E_n , Δx_i with corresponding uncertainty U_i , d_i and χ_{obs} has been calculated using the same procedure as shown in chapter 3.1 and are shown in Tables 15-18.

Table 10: The weighed mean of CF and corresponding standard uncertainty of all results. Note that above 10 kHz only the results from CMI were available.

Href	f	AFwm	N
[A/m]	[MHz]	[/]	[/]
0,15	30	1,06	0,01
0,15	50	0,89	0,01
0,15	70	0,91	0,01
0,15	100	0,96	0,01
0,15	200	0,99	0,02
0,15	300	1,01	0,02
0,15	400	1,00	0,02
0,05	500	0,98	0,03
0,05	600	0,97	0,03
0,1	700	0,95	0,03
0,1	800	0,96	0,03
0,1	900	0,93	0,03
0,1	1000	0,96	0,03

Table 15: The Degree of Equivalence E_n .

H_{ref}	f	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CMi	IMBiH
		E_n	E_n	E_n	E_n	E_n
[A/m]	[MHz]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
0,15	30	0,86	-1,39	0,00	0,78	/
0,15	50	1,36	-2,61	0,70	1,05	/
0,15	70	0,60	-2,00	0,74	0,96	/
0,15	100	-0,47	/	0,16	0,29	/
0,15	200	-0,19	/	-0,49	0,70	/
0,15	300	-0,10	/	-0,26	0,46	/
0,15	400	-0,05	/	-0,17	0,25	/
0,05	500	-0,15	/	-0,29	0,50	/
0,05	600	-0,43	/	0,24	0,15	/
0,1	700	-0,54	/	0,34	0,14	/
0,1	800	-0,35	/	-0,26	0,66	/
0,1	900	/	/	0,40	-0,40	/
0,1	1000	/	/	-0,34	0,34	/

Table 16: The x_i and corresponding uncertainty U_i .

H_{ref}	f	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CMi	IMBiH	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CMi	IMBiH
		Δx_i	Δx_i	Δx_i	Δx_i	Δx_i	U_i	U_i	U_i	U_i	U_i
[A/m]	[MHz]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
0,15	30	0,051	-0,056	0,000	0,041	0	0,059	0,040	0,045	0,053	0
0,15	50	0,070	-0,082	0,027	0,048	0	0,051	0,032	0,039	0,045	0
0,15	70	0,030	-0,066	0,030	0,044	0	0,050	0,033	0,040	0,046	0
0,15	100	-0,022	0	0,006	0,013	0	0,046	0	0,038	0,044	0
0,15	200	-0,009	0	-0,018	0,032	0	0,048	0	0,037	0,046	0
0,15	300	-0,011	0	-0,007	0,053	0	0,106	0	0,025	0,115	0
0,15	400	-0,005	0	-0,005	0,025	0	0,106	0	0,027	0,097	0
0,05	500	-0,015	0	-0,015	0,051	0	0,095	0	0,053	0,102	0
0,05	600	-0,040	0	0,014	0,013	0	0,092	0	0,057	0,087	0
0,1	700	-0,048	0	0,019	0,012	0	0,088	0	0,056	0,082	0
0,1	800	-0,033	0	-0,014	0,063	0	0,092	0	0,053	0,096	0
0,1	900	0	0	0,019	-0,030	0	0	0	0,046	0,076	0
0,1	1000	0	0	-0,015	0,030	0	0	0	0,043	0,089	0

Table 17: The d_i parameter (exclusion of incompatible results)

H_{ref}	f	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CMi	IMBiH
		d_i	d_i	d_i	d_i	d_i
[A/m]	[MHz]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
0,15	30	1,72	-2,79	0,00	1,56	/
0,15	50	2,73	-5,23	1,39	2,10	/
0,15	70	1,20	-4,01	1,48	1,91	/
0,15	100	-0,94	/	0,32	0,58	/
0,15	200	-0,38	/	-0,98	1,41	/
0,15	300	-0,21	/	-0,52	0,92	/
0,15	400	-0,09	/	-0,34	0,51	/
0,05	500	-0,30	/	-0,58	1,00	/
0,05	600	-0,86	/	0,49	0,29	/
0,1	700	-1,08	/	0,69	0,28	/
0,1	800	-0,70	/	-0,52	1,33	/
0,1	900	/	/	0,80	-0,80	/
0,1	1000	/	/	-0,68	0,68	/

Table 18: Consistency of results

<i>Href</i>	<i>f</i>	χ_{obs}^2	<i>N</i>	<i>chidist</i>
[A/m]	[MHz]	[/]	[/]	[/]
0,15	30	9,58	4	0,02
0,15	50	28,70	4	0,00
0,15	70	16,28	4	0,00
0,15	100	0,92	3	0,63
0,15	200	2,04	3	0,36
0,15	300	0,85	3	0,65
0,15	400	0,26	3	0,88
0,05	500	1,01	3	0,60
0,05	600	0,74	3	0,69
0,1	700	1,18	3	0,55
0,1	800	1,84	3	0,40
0,1	900	0,64	2	0,42
0,1	1000	0,46	2	0,50

In this case the consistency of results failed for 0.15 A/m measurement at 30 MHz, 50 MHz and 70 MHz, therefore the laboratory with the highest d_i (Table 17) should be excluded from the intercomparison.

The same analysis has been repeated and the results with uncertainties (normal distribution, $k=1$), the weighed mean of CF with standard uncertainty, *Degrees of Equivalence* E_n , Δx_i with corresponding uncertainty U_i , d_i and χ_{obs} has been recalculated using the same procedure as shown in chapter 3.1 and are shown in Tables 19-24. In this case a good agreement of results has been obtained ($\chi_i > 0.05$, Table 24), therefore no further exclusion of the results is necessary. Additionally, the results are also shown in Figs. 16-28 for each measured point.

Table 19: The results measured by the partners. All uncertainties have normal distribution with $k=1$. In this case, RISE measurement at 0.15 A/m at 30 MHz, 50 MHz and 70 MHz are excluded from the analysis.

<i>Href</i>	<i>f</i>	SIQ		RISE		TUBITAK		CMI		IMBiH	
		<i>CF</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>CF</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>CF</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>CF</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>CF</i>	<i>N</i>
[A/m]	[MHz]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
0,15	30	1,11	0,03	/	/	1,06	0,03	1,10	0,03	/	/
0,15	50	0,96	0,03	/	/	0,92	0,02	0,94	0,03	/	/
0,15	70	0,94	0,03	/	/	0,94	0,02	0,95	0,03	/	/
0,15	100	0,94	0,03	/	/	0,97	0,02	0,98	0,03	/	/
0,15	200	0,98	0,03	/	/	0,97	0,02	1,02	0,03	/	/
0,15	300	1,00	0,06	/	/	1,00	0,02	1,06	0,06	/	/
0,15	400	1,00	0,06	/	/	1,00	0,02	1,03	0,05	/	/
0,05	500	0,96	0,06	/	/	0,96	0,04	1,03	0,06	/	/
0,05	600	0,93	0,05	/	/	0,99	0,04	0,99	0,05	/	/
0,1	700	0,90	0,05	/	/	0,96	0,04	0,96	0,05	/	/
0,1	800	0,93	0,05	/	/	0,95	0,04	1,03	0,05	/	/
0,1	900	/	/	/	/	0,95	0,04	0,90	0,05	/	/
0,1	1000	/	/	/	/	0,95	0,04	0,99	0,05	/	/

Table 20: The weighed mean of CF and corresponding standard uncertainty of all results. In this case, RISE measurement at 0.15 A/m at 30 MHz, 50 MHz and 70 MHz are excluded from the analysis.

H_{ref}	f	AF_{wm}	N
[A/m]	[MHz]	[/]	[/]
0,15	30	1,09	0,02
0,15	50	0,94	0,01
0,15	70	0,94	0,01
0,15	100	0,96	0,01
0,15	200	0,99	0,02
0,15	300	1,01	0,02
0,15	400	1,00	0,02
0,05	500	0,98	0,03
0,05	600	0,97	0,03
0,1	700	0,95	0,03
0,1	800	0,96	0,03
0,1	900	0,93	0,03
0,1	1000	0,96	0,03

Table 21: The *Degree of Equivalence* E_n . In this case, RISE measurement at 0.15 A/m at 30 MHz, 50 MHz and 70 MHz are excluded from the analysis.

H_{ref}	f	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CMR	IMBiH
		E_n	E_n	E_n	E_n	E_n
[A/m]	[MHz]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
0,15	30	0,43	/	-0,66	0,29	/
0,15	50	0,51	/	-0,51	0,06	/
0,15	70	-0,10	/	-0,13	0,23	/
0,15	100	-0,47	/	0,16	0,29	/
0,15	200	-0,19	/	-0,49	0,70	/
0,15	300	-0,10	/	-0,26	0,46	/
0,15	400	-0,05	/	-0,17	0,25	/
0,05	500	-0,15	/	-0,29	0,50	/
0,05	600	-0,43	/	0,24	0,15	/
0,1	700	-0,54	/	0,34	0,14	/
0,1	800	-0,35	/	-0,26	0,66	/
0,1	900	/	/	0,40	-0,40	/
0,1	1000	/	/	-0,34	0,34	/

Table 22: The x_i and corresponding uncertainty U_i . In this case, RISE measurement at 0.15 A/m at 30 MHz, 50 MHz and 70 MHz are excluded from the analysis.

H_{ref}	f	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CM	IMBiH	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CM	IMBiH
[A/m]	[MHz]	Δx_i	Δx_i	Δx_i	Δx_i	Δx_i	U_i	U_i	U_i	U_i	U_i
		[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
0,15	30	0,024	0	-0,027	0,014	0	0,056	0	0,040	0,049	0
0,15	50	0,024	0	-0,018	0,002	0	0,048	0	0,035	0,042	0
0,15	70	-0,004	0	-0,005	0,010	0	0,047	0	0,036	0,043	0
0,15	100	-0,022	0	0,006	0,013	0	0,046	0	0,038	0,044	0
0,15	200	-0,009	0	-0,018	0,032	0	0,048	0	0,037	0,046	0
0,15	300	-0,011	0	-0,007	0,053	0	0,106	0	0,025	0,115	0
0,15	400	-0,005	0	-0,005	0,025	0	0,106	0	0,027	0,097	0
0,05	500	-0,015	0	-0,015	0,051	0	0,095	0	0,053	0,102	0
0,05	600	-0,040	0	0,014	0,013	0	0,092	0	0,057	0,087	0
0,1	700	-0,048	0	0,019	0,012	0	0,088	0	0,056	0,082	0
0,1	800	-0,033	0	-0,014	0,063	0	0,092	0	0,053	0,096	0
0,1	900	0	0	0,019	-0,030	0	0	0	0,046	0,076	0
0,1	1000	0	0	-0,015	0,030	0	0	0	0,043	0,089	0

Table 23: The d_i parameter (exclusion of incompatible results). In this case, RISE measurement at 0.15 A/m at 30 MHz, 50 MHz and 70 MHz are excluded from the analysis.

H_{ref}	f	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CM	IMBiH
[A/m]	[MHz]	d_i	d_i	d_i	d_i	d_i
		[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
0,15	30	0,86	/	-1,33	0,58	/
0,15	50	1,02	/	-1,03	0,11	/
0,15	70	-0,19	/	-0,25	0,45	/
0,15	100	-0,94	/	0,32	0,58	/
0,15	200	-0,38	/	-0,98	1,41	/
0,15	300	-0,21	/	-0,52	0,92	/
0,15	400	-0,09	/	-0,34	0,51	/
0,05	500	-0,30	/	-0,58	1,00	/
0,05	600	-0,86	/	0,49	0,29	/
0,1	700	-1,08	/	0,69	0,28	/
0,1	800	-0,70	/	-0,52	1,33	/
0,1	900	/	/	0,80	-0,80	/
0,1	1000	/	/	-0,68	0,68	/

Table 24: Consistency of results. In this case, RISE measurement at 0.15 A/m at 30 MHz, 50 MHz and 70 MHz are excluded from the analysis.

<i>Href</i>	<i>f</i>	x_{obs}^2	<i>N</i>	<i>chidist</i>
[A/m]	[MHz]	[/]	[/]	[/]
0,15	30	1,81	3	0,40
0,15	50	1,39	3	0,50
0,15	70	0,20	3	0,90
0,15	100	0,92	3	0,63
0,15	200	2,04	3	0,36
0,15	300	0,85	3	0,65
0,15	400	0,26	3	0,88
0,05	500	1,01	3	0,60
0,05	600	0,74	3	0,69
0,1	700	1,18	3	0,55
0,1	800	1,84	3	0,40
0,1	900	0,64	2	0,42
0,1	1000	0,46	2	0,50

Fig. 16: Degrees of Equivalence for Narda HF-0191probe at 0.15 A/m and 30 MHz.

Fig. 17: Degrees of Equivalence for Narda HF-0191 probe at 0.15 A/m and 50 MHz.

Fig. 18: Degrees of Equivalence for Narda HF-0191 probe at 0.15 A/m and 70 MHz.

Fig. 19: Degrees of Equivalence for Narda HF-0191 probe at 0.15 A/m and 100 MHz.

Fig. 20: Degrees of Equivalence for Narda HF-0191 probe at 0.15 A/m and 200 MHz.

Fig. 21: Degrees of Equivalence for Narda HF-0191 probe at 0.15 A/m and 300 MHz.

Fig. 22: Degrees of Equivalence for Narda HF-0191 probe at 0.15 A/m and 400 MHz.

Fig. 23: Degrees of Equivalence for Narda HF-0191probe at 0.05 A/m and 500 MHz.

Fig. 24: Degrees of Equivalence for Narda HF-0191probe at 0.05 A/m and 600 MHz.

Fig. 25: Degrees of Equivalence for Narda HF-0191 probe at 0.10 A/m and 700 MHz.

Fig. 26: Degrees of Equivalence for Narda HF-0191 probe at 0.10 A/m and 800 MHz.

Fig. 27: Degrees of Equivalence for Narda HF-0191probe at 0.10 A/m and 900 MHz.

Fig. 28: Degrees of Equivalence for Narda HF-0191probe at 0.10 A/m and 1000 MHz.

3.3 Probe EFA-300

The next probe that has been analysed is Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe. The same analysis has been repeated and the results with uncertainties (normal distribution, $k=1$), the weighed mean of CF with standard uncertainty, *Degrees of Equivalence* E_n , Δx_i with corresponding uncertainty U_i , d_i and χ_{obs} has been calculated using the same procedure as shown in chapter 3.1 and are shown in Tables 25-30. In this case a good agreement of results has been obtained ($\chi_i > 0.05$, Table 30), therefore no further exclusion of the results is necessary. Additionally, the results are also shown in Figs. 29-49 for each measured point.

Table 25: The results measured by the partners. All uncertainties have normal distribution with $k=1$.

E_{ref}	f	SIQ		RISE		TUBITAK		CMH		IMBiH	
		CF	N	CF	N	CF	N	CF	N	AF	N
[V/m]	[kHz]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
50	0,01	1,01	0,01	/	/	0,98	0,03	1,01	0,01	0,973	0,054
50	0,02	0,99	0,01	/	/	0,97	0,03	1,00	0,01	0,955	0,052
500	0,02	1,00	0,01	/	/	/	/	1,00	0,01	1,026	0,016
100	0,05	0,99	0,01	/	/	0,99	0,02	1,00	0,01	0,956	0,026
1000	0,05	1,00	0,01	/	/	0,99	0,02	1,00	0,01	/	/
2000	0,05	1,00	0,01	/	/	1,00	0,02	1,00	0,01	/	/
50	0,1	0,99	0,01	/	/	0,96	0,03	0,99	0,01	0,952	0,052
50	0,4	0,99	0,01	/	/	0,96	0,03	0,99	0,01	0,955	0,052
50	1	0,99	0,01	/	/	0,96	0,03	0,99	0,01	0,961	0,053
1000	1	1,00	0,01	/	/	/	/	1,00	0,01	/	/
50	5	0,99	0,01	/	/	0,97	0,03	0,99	0,01	0,972	0,054
50	7	0,99	0,01	/	/	0,97	0,03	1,00	0,01	/	/
50	10	1,00	0,01	/	/	0,98	0,03	1,00	0,01	0,984	0,055
1000	10	0,99	0,01	0,99	0,02	/	/	0,99	0,01	/	/
50	15	1,01	0,01	0,97	0,02	0,99	0,03	1,02	0,01	1,000	0,057
50	20	1,03	0,01	0,99	0,02	1,01	0,03	1,04	0,01	1,022	0,060
50	23	1,05	0,01	1,01	0,02	1,04	0,03	1,07	0,01	/	/
50	25	1,08	0,02	1,04	0,03	1,06	0,03	1,09	0,02	1,073	0,066
50	27	1,13	0,02	1,09	0,03	1,11	0,03	1,14	0,02	/	/
50	30	1,28	0,02	1,23	0,03	1,26	0,04	1,29	0,02	1,271	0,092
500	30	1,28	0,02	/	/	/	/	1,29	0,01	1,279	0,011

Table 26: The weighed mean of CF and corresponding standard uncertainty of all results.

E_{ref}	f	AF_{wm}	N
[V/m]	[kHz]	[/]	[/]
50	0,01	1,005	0,01
50	0,02	0,990	0,01
500	0,02	1,008	0,01
100	0,05	0,994	0,01
1000	0,05	1,002	0,01
2000	0,05	1,003	0,01
50	0,1	0,987	0,01
50	0,4	0,986	0,01
50	1	0,987	0,01
1000	1	1,000	0,01
50	5	0,989	0,01
50	7	0,992	0,01
50	10	0,997	0,01
1000	10	0,991	0,01
50	15	1,006	0,01
50	20	1,028	0,01
50	23	1,051	0,01
50	25	1,078	0,01
50	27	1,127	0,01
50	30	1,274	0,01
500	30	1,285	0,01

Table 27: The Degree of Equivalence E_n .

E_{ref}	f	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	GMI	IMBiH
E_n	E_n	E_n	E_n	E_n	E_n	E_n
[V/m]	[kHz]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
50	0,01	0,13	/	-0,49	0,28	-0,30
50	0,02	0,10	/	-0,38	0,26	-0,34
500	0,02	-0,30	/	/	-0,26	0,64
100	0,05	0,00	/	-0,11	0,49	-0,76
1000	0,05	-0,03	/	-0,30	0,23	/
2000	0,05	-0,07	/	-0,08	0,12	/
50	0,1	0,14	/	-0,52	0,31	-0,34
50	0,4	0,11	/	-0,51	0,30	-0,30
50	1	0,07	/	-0,52	0,33	-0,25
1000	1	-0,12	/	/	0,12	/
50	5	-0,05	/	-0,35	0,31	-0,15
50	7	-0,09	/	-0,41	0,34	/
50	10	-0,10	/	-0,34	0,34	-0,12
1000	10	-0,26	-0,03	/	0,26	/
50	15	0,14	-0,83	-0,31	0,62	-0,06
50	20	0,16	-0,84	-0,32	0,63	-0,05
50	23	0,14	-0,90	-0,28	0,66	/
50	25	0,16	-0,81	-0,31	0,61	-0,04
50	27	0,14	-0,77	-0,29	0,59	/
50	30	0,25	-0,81	-0,21	0,53	-0,01
500	30	-0,14	/	/	0,48	-0,36

Table 28: The Δx_i and corresponding uncertainty U_i .

E_{ref}	f	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CMI	IMBiH	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CMI	IMBiH
[V/m]	[kHz]	Δx_i	Δx_i	Δx_i	Δx_i	Δx_i	U_i	U_i	U_i	U_i	U_i
		[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
50	0,01	0,003	0	-0,025	0,005	-0,032	0,022	0	0,052	0,020	0,106
50	0,02	0,002	0	-0,020	0,005	-0,035	0,022	0	0,052	0,019	0,102
500	0,02	-0,007	0	0	-0,004	0,018	0,024	0	0	0,013	0,028
100	0,05	0,000	0	-0,004	0,007	-0,038	0,024	0	0,039	0,014	0,050
1000	0,05	-0,001	0	-0,012	0,003	0	0,024	0	0,039	0,013	0
2000	0,05	-0,002	0	-0,003	0,001	0	0,024	0	0,040	0,013	0
50	0,1	0,003	0	-0,027	0,006	-0,035	0,022	0	0,051	0,019	0,102
50	0,4	0,002	0	-0,026	0,006	-0,031	0,022	0	0,051	0,018	0,103
50	1	0,001	0	-0,027	0,006	-0,026	0,022	0	0,051	0,018	0,104
1000	1	-0,003	0	0	0,001	0	0,023	0	0	0,011	0
50	5	-0,001	0	-0,018	0,006	-0,016	0,022	0	0,052	0,018	0,106
50	7	-0,002	0	-0,021	0,006	0	0,022	0	0,052	0,018	0
50	10	-0,002	0	-0,018	0,006	-0,013	0,022	0	0,052	0,018	0,109
1000	10	-0,006	-0,00137	0	0,003	0	0,024	0,046	0	0,011	0
50	15	0,003	-0,03633	-0,017	0,012	-0,007	0,023	0,044	0,053	0,020	0,113
50	20	0,004	-0,03765	-0,017	0,013	-0,005	0,023	0,045	0,054	0,021	0,118
50	23	0,003	-0,04094	-0,016	0,014	0	0,024	0,045	0,056	0,022	0
50	25	0,004	-0,03807	-0,018	0,015	-0,005	0,024	0,047	0,057	0,024	0,130
50	27	0,004	-0,03743	-0,017	0,015	0	0,025	0,049	0,059	0,026	0
50	30	0,007	-0,04414	-0,014	0,020	-0,003	0,027	0,055	0,067	0,038	0,183
500	30	-0,005	0	0	0,009	-0,006	0,033	0	0	0,019	0,016

Table 29: The d_i parameter (exclusion of incompatible results)

E_{ref}	f	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CMI	IMBiH
[V/m]	[kHz]	d_i	d_i	d_i	d_i	d_i
		[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
50	0,01	0,25	/	-0,97	0,56	-0,61
50	0,02	0,20	/	-0,77	0,52	-0,69
500	0,02	-0,60	/	/	-0,53	1,29
100	0,05	-0,01	/	-0,22	0,98	-1,53
1000	0,05	-0,05	/	-0,61	0,46	/
2000	0,05	-0,14	/	-0,16	0,24	/
50	0,1	0,27	/	-1,04	0,61	-0,68
50	0,4	0,21	/	-1,01	0,61	-0,61
50	1	0,13	/	-1,04	0,67	-0,50
1000	1	-0,24	/	/	0,24	/
50	5	-0,10	/	-0,70	0,62	-0,31
50	7	-0,18	/	-0,82	0,67	/
50	10	-0,20	/	-0,68	0,68	-0,24
1000	10	-0,52	-0,06	/	0,52	/
50	15	0,28	-1,66	-0,62	1,25	-0,12
50	20	0,32	-1,69	-0,64	1,26	-0,09
50	23	0,27	-1,80	-0,57	1,33	/
50	25	0,32	-1,63	-0,62	1,23	-0,08
50	27	0,29	-1,53	-0,57	1,18	/
50	30	0,50	-1,62	-0,41	1,06	-0,03
500	30	-0,29	/	/	0,96	-0,72

Table 30: Consistency of results

<i>E_{ref}</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>x_{obs}²</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>chidist</i>
[V/m]	[kHz]	[/]	[/]	[/]
50	0,01	1,41	4	0,70
50	0,02	1,16	4	0,76
500	0,02	1,71	3	0,43
100	0,05	2,66	4	0,45
1000	0,05	0,41	3	0,81
2000	0,05	0,06	3	0,97
50	0,1	1,67	4	0,64
50	0,4	1,50	4	0,68
50	1	1,45	4	0,69
1000	1	0,06	2	0,81
50	5	0,74	3	0,69
50	7	0,84	3	0,66
50	10	0,73	4	0,87
1000	10	0,30	3	0,86
50	15	3,72	5	0,44
50	20	3,87	5	0,42
50	23	4,20	4	0,24
50	25	3,65	5	0,46
50	27	3,24	4	0,36
50	30	3,30	5	0,51
500	30	0,92	3	0,63

Fig. 29: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 50 V/m and 0.01 kHz.

Fig. 30: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 50 V/m and 0.02 kHz.

Fig. 31: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 500 V/m and 0.02 kHz.

Fig. 32: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 100 V/m and 0.05 kHz.

Fig. 33: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 1000 V/m and 0.05 kHz.

Fig. 34: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 2000 V/m and 0.05 kHz.

Fig. 35: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 50 V/m and 0.1 kHz.

Fig. 36: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 50 V/m and 0.4 kHz.

Fig. 37: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 50 V/m and 1 kHz.

Fig. 38: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 1000 V/m and 1 kHz.

Fig. 39: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 50 V/m and 5 kHz.

Fig. 40: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 50 V/m and 7 kHz.

Fig. 41: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 50 V/m and 10 kHz.

Fig. 42: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 1000 V/m and 10 kHz.

Fig. 43: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 50 V/m and 15 kHz.

Fig. 44: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 50 V/m and 20 kHz.

Fig. 45: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 50 V/m and 23 kHz.

Fig. 46: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 50 V/m and 25 kHz.

Fig. 47: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 50 V/m and 27 kHz.

Fig. 48: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 50 V/m and 30 kHz.

Fig. 49: Degrees of equivalence for Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300 probe at 500 V/m and 30 kHz.

3.4 Probe HI-6053

The last probe that has been analysed is ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe. The same analysis has been repeated and the results with uncertainties (normal distribution, $k=1$), the weighed mean of CF with standard uncertainty, *Degrees of Equivalence* E_n , Δx_i with corresponding uncertainty U_i , d_i and χ_{obs} has been calculated using the same procedure as shown in Chapter 3.1 and are shown in Tables 31-36.

In this case the consistency of results failed again for 20 V/m measurement at 18 GHz (Table 36), therefore the laboratory with the highest d_i (Table 35, RISE) should be excluded from the intercomparison.

The same analysis has been repeated and the results with uncertainties (normal distribution, $k=1$), the weighed mean of CF with standard uncertainty, *Degrees of Equivalence* E_n , Δx_i with corresponding uncertainty U_i , d_i and χ_{obs} has been recalculated using the same procedure as shown in Chapter 3.1 and are shown in Tables 37-42. In this case a good agreement of results has been obtained ($\chi_i > 0.05$, Table 42), therefore no further exclusion of the results is necessary. Additionally, the results are also shown in Figs. 50-78 for each measured point.

Table 31: The results measured by the partners. All uncertainties have normal distribution with $k=1$.

E_{ref}	f	SIQ		RISE		TUBITAK		CMH		IMBiH	
		CF	N	CF	N	CF	N	CF	N	CF	N
[V/m]	[GHz]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
20	0,01	/	/	1,53	0,04	/	/	1,49	0,04	/	/
20	0,03	/	/	0,97	0,02	0,95	0,03	0,97	0,03	/	/
20	0,05	/	/	0,92	0,02	0,88	0,03	0,90	0,02	/	/
20	0,07	/	/	0,92	0,05	0,87	0,03	0,89	0,02	/	/
20	0,1	/	/	0,83	0,05	0,88	0,03	0,90	0,02	/	/
20	0,2	/	/	0,84	0,05	0,93	0,03	0,92	0,03	/	/
20	0,3	/	/	0,89	0,05	0,94	0,03	0,95	0,05	/	/
20	0,5	/	/	0,92	0,05	0,89	0,04	0,99	0,05	/	/
20	0,7	/	/	0,90	0,05	0,95	0,04	0,99	0,06	/	/
20	0,9	/	/	0,91	0,05	1,02	0,04	1,04	0,06	/	/
20	1	/	/	1,01	0,06	/	/	1,04	0,06	/	/
20	1,5	/	/	1,02	0,05	/	/	1,02	0,06	/	/
20	2	/	/	1,16	0,06	1,06	0,03	1,06	0,06	/	/
20	2,45	/	/	1,17	0,06	1,03	0,03	1,04	0,06	/	/
20	3	/	/	1,20	0,06	1,14	0,03	1,03	0,06	/	/
20	4	/	/	1,10	0,06	1,02	0,03	1,06	0,05	/	/
20	5	/	/	1,08	0,06	1,05	0,03	1,06	0,05	/	/
20	6	/	/	1,14	0,06	1,02	0,03	1,13	0,05	/	/
20	7	/	/	1,06	0,05	0,97	0,03	1,07	0,06	/	/
20	8	/	/	1,05	0,05	0,96	0,03	1,03	0,05	/	/
20	9	/	/	1,13	0,06	1,00	0,03	1,04	0,05	/	/
20	13	/	/	0,97	0,06	0,90	0,03	0,86	0,04	/	/
20	18	/	/	0,92	0,05	0,77	0,02	0,83	0,04	/	/
20	20	/	/	0,85	0,06	/	/	0,75	0,04	/	/
20	25	/	/	0,79	0,05	/	/	0,73	0,04	/	/
20	27	/	/	/	/	0,73	0,02	0,74	0,04	/	/
20	30	/	/	/	/	0,86	0,03	0,85	0,04	/	/
20	35	/	/	/	/	1,03	0,03	1,05	0,06	/	/
20	40	/	/	/	/	1,29	0,04	1,21	0,08	/	/

Table 32: The weighed mean of CF and corresponding standard uncertainty of all results. Note that above 10 kHz only the results from CMI were available.

E_{ref} [V/m]	f [GHz]	CF_{wm} [μ]	N [μ]
20	0,01	1,51	0,03
20	0,03	0,97	0,02
20	0,05	0,91	0,01
20	0,07	0,89	0,02
20	0,1	0,88	0,02
20	0,2	0,91	0,02
20	0,3	0,93	0,02
20	0,5	0,92	0,03
20	0,7	0,94	0,03
20	0,9	0,99	0,03
20	1	1,02	0,04
20	1,5	1,02	0,04
20	2	1,08	0,02
20	2,45	1,06	0,02
20	3	1,13	0,03
20	4	1,04	0,02
20	5	1,06	0,02
20	6	1,06	0,02
20	7	1,00	0,02
20	8	0,99	0,02
20	9	1,03	0,02
20	13	0,90	0,02
20	18	0,80	0,02
20	20	0,78	0,03
20	25	0,75	0,03
20	27	0,74	0,02
20	30	0,86	0,02
20	35	1,03	0,03
20	40	1,28	0,03

Table 33: The Degree of Equivalence E_n .

E_{ref}	f	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CM	IMBiH
		E_n	E_n	E_n	E_n	E_n
[V/m]	[GHz]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
20	0,01	/	0,35	/	-0,35	/
20	0,03	/	0,08	-0,30	0,18	/
20	0,05	/	0,41	-0,44	-0,04	/
20	0,07	/	0,32	-0,30	0,07	/
20	0,1	/	-0,62	-0,06	0,51	/
20	0,2	/	-0,86	0,29	0,36	/
20	0,3	/	-0,47	0,22	0,23	/
20	0,5	/	0,00	-0,63	0,76	/
20	0,7	/	-0,52	0,08	0,47	/
20	0,9	/	-0,97	0,45	0,53	/
20	1	/	-0,18	/	0,18	/
20	1,5	/	-0,03	/	0,03	/
20	2	/	0,76	-0,48	-0,15	/
20	2,45	/	1,03	-0,72	-0,11	/
20	3	/	0,63	0,27	-0,93	/
20	4	/	0,57	-0,59	0,18	/
20	5	/	0,21	-0,21	0,06	/
20	6	/	0,71	-1,14	0,71	/
20	7	/	0,57	-0,91	0,59	/
20	8	/	0,59	-0,84	0,46	/
20	9	/	0,91	-0,79	0,12	/
20	13	/	0,63	0,00	-0,53	/
20	18	/	1,20	-1,17	0,38	/
20	20	/	0,68	/	-0,68	/
20	25	/	0,51	/	-0,51	/
20	27	/	/	-0,12	0,12	/
20	30	/	/	0,10	-0,10	/
20	35	/	/	-0,14	0,14	/
20	40	/	/	0,50	-0,50	/

Table 34: The x_i and corresponding uncertainty U_i .

E_{ref}	f	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CMI	IMBiH	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CMI	IMBiH
[V/m]	[GHz]	Δx_i	Δx_i	Δx_i	Δx_i	Δx_i	U_i	U_i	U_i	U_i	U_i
		[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
20	0,01	0	0,017	0	-0,022	0	0	0,049	0	0,061	0
20	0,03	0	0,003	-0,018	0,008	0	0	0,035	0,060	0,044	0
20	0,05	0	0,014	-0,024	-0,002	0	0	0,033	0,056	0,040	0
20	0,07	0	0,030	-0,015	0,002	0	0	0,094	0,051	0,034	0
20	0,1	0	-0,052	-0,003	0,017	0	0	0,083	0,052	0,034	0
20	0,2	0	-0,072	0,016	0,013	0	0	0,084	0,055	0,035	0
20	0,3	0	-0,040	0,010	0,021	0	0	0,084	0,046	0,091	0
20	0,5	0	0,000	-0,031	0,074	0	0	0,087	0,049	0,097	0
20	0,7	0	-0,043	0,004	0,046	0	0	0,083	0,054	0,098	0
20	0,9	0	-0,080	0,026	0,055	0	0	0,083	0,059	0,103	0
20	1	0	-0,014	0	0,015	0	0	0,077	0	0,083	0
20	1,5	0	-0,002	0	0,002	0	0	0,073	0	0,082	0
20	2	0	0,083	-0,018	-0,015	0	0	0,109	0,037	0,106	0
20	2,45	0	0,114	-0,025	-0,012	0	0	0,111	0,035	0,107	0
20	3	0	0,071	0,011	-0,099	0	0	0,113	0,041	0,106	0
20	4	0	0,059	-0,022	0,016	0	0	0,104	0,037	0,089	0
20	5	0	0,021	-0,008	0,005	0	0	0,101	0,039	0,088	0
20	6	0	0,077	-0,041	0,068	0	0	0,108	0,036	0,095	0
20	7	0	0,056	-0,030	0,068	0	0	0,099	0,033	0,114	0
20	8	0	0,059	-0,029	0,043	0	0	0,099	0,034	0,093	0
20	9	0	0,097	-0,028	0,011	0	0	0,107	0,036	0,091	0
20	13	0	0,065	0,000	-0,042	0	0	0,103	0,032	0,079	0
20	18	0	0,119	-0,030	0,029	0	0	0,099	0,026	0,076	0
20	20	0	0,066	0	-0,030	0	0	0,097	0	0,045	0
20	25	0	0,045	0	-0,024	0	0	0,089	0	0,046	0
20	27	0	0	-0,003	0,008	0	0	0	0,022	0,063	0
20	30	0	0	0,003	-0,007	0	0	0	0,027	0,070	0
20	35	0	0	-0,004	0,014	0	0	0	0,029	0,099	0
20	40	0	0	0,017	-0,068	0	0	0	0,034	0,137	0

Table 35: The d_i parameter (exclusion of incompatible results)

E_{ref}	f	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CIM	IMBiH
[V/m]	[GHz]	d_i	d_i	d_i	d_i	d_i
		[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
20	0,01	/	0,70	/	-0,70	/
20	0,03	/	0,15	-0,59	0,35	/
20	0,05	/	0,81	-0,88	-0,09	/
20	0,07	/	0,64	-0,59	0,13	/
20	0,1	/	-1,25	-0,12	1,01	/
20	0,2	/	-1,71	0,58	0,72	/
20	0,3	/	-0,94	0,43	0,46	/
20	0,5	/	0,00	-1,26	1,53	/
20	0,7	/	-1,04	0,15	0,94	/
20	0,9	/	-1,93	0,89	1,07	/
20	1	/	-0,36	/	0,36	/
20	1,5	/	-0,06	/	0,06	/
20	2	/	1,52	-0,96	-0,29	/
20	2,45	/	2,06	-1,43	-0,23	/
20	3	/	1,26	0,53	-1,86	/
20	4	/	1,14	-1,19	0,36	/
20	5	/	0,41	-0,42	0,12	/
20	6	/	1,42	-2,27	1,42	/
20	7	/	1,13	-1,82	1,19	/
20	8	/	1,19	-1,68	0,92	/
20	9	/	1,81	-1,57	0,24	/
20	13	/	1,26	0,00	-1,06	/
20	18	/	2,40	-2,35	0,76	/
20	20	/	1,36	/	-1,36	/
20	25	/	1,01	/	-1,01	/
20	27	/	/	-0,24	0,24	/
20	30	/	/	0,20	-0,20	/
20	35	/	/	-0,28	0,28	/
20	40	/	/	0,99	-0,99	/

Table 36: Consistency of results

<i>Eref</i>	<i>f</i>	x_{obs}^2	<i>N</i>	<i>chidist</i>
[V/m]	[GHz]	[/]	[/]	[/]
20	0,01	0,49	2	0,48
20	0,03	0,37	3	0,83
20	0,05	0,98	3	0,61
20	0,07	0,60	3	0,74
20	0,1	1,82	3	0,40
20	0,2	2,93	3	0,23
20	0,3	0,92	3	0,63
20	0,5	2,59	3	0,27
20	0,7	1,48	3	0,48
20	0,9	3,89	3	0,14
20	1	0,13	2	0,72
20	1,5	0,00	2	0,95
20	2	2,30	3	0,32
20	2,45	4,30	3	0,12
20	3	4,18	3	0,12
20	4	1,73	3	0,42
20	5	0,22	3	0,89
20	6	5,18	3	0,07
20	7	3,35	3	0,19
20	8	2,87	3	0,24
20	9	3,71	3	0,16
20	13	2,24	3	0,33
20	18	7,28	3	0,03
20	20	1,85	2	0,17
20	25	1,02	2	0,31
20	27	0,06	2	0,81
20	30	0,04	2	0,84
20	35	0,08	2	0,78
20	40	0,99	2	0,32

Table 37: The results measured by the partners. All uncertainties have normal distribution with $k=1$. In this case, RISE measurement at 20 V/m at 18 GHz is excluded from the analysis.

<i>E_{ref}</i>	<i>f</i>	SIQ		RISE		TUBITAK		CMJ		IMBiH	
		CF	N	CF	N	CF	N	CF	N	CF	N
[V/m]	[GHz]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
20	0,01	/	/	1,53	0,04	/	/	1,49	0,04	/	/
20	0,03	/	/	0,97	0,02	0,95	0,03	0,97	0,03	/	/
20	0,05	/	/	0,92	0,02	0,88	0,03	0,90	0,02	/	/
20	0,07	/	/	0,92	0,05	0,87	0,03	0,89	0,02	/	/
20	0,1	/	/	0,83	0,05	0,88	0,03	0,90	0,02	/	/
20	0,2	/	/	0,84	0,05	0,93	0,03	0,92	0,03	/	/
20	0,3	/	/	0,89	0,05	0,94	0,03	0,95	0,05	/	/
20	0,5	/	/	0,92	0,05	0,89	0,04	0,99	0,05	/	/
20	0,7	/	/	0,90	0,05	0,95	0,04	0,99	0,06	/	/
20	0,9	/	/	0,91	0,05	1,02	0,04	1,04	0,06	/	/
20	1	/	/	1,01	0,06	/	/	1,04	0,06	/	/
20	1,5	/	/	1,02	0,05	/	/	1,02	0,06	/	/
20	2	/	/	1,16	0,06	1,06	0,03	1,06	0,06	/	/
20	2,45	/	/	1,17	0,06	1,03	0,03	1,04	0,06	/	/
20	3	/	/	1,20	0,06	1,14	0,03	1,03	0,06	/	/
20	4	/	/	1,10	0,06	1,02	0,03	1,06	0,05	/	/
20	5	/	/	1,08	0,06	1,05	0,03	1,06	0,05	/	/
20	6	/	/	1,14	0,06	1,02	0,03	1,13	0,05	/	/
20	7	/	/	1,06	0,05	0,97	0,03	1,07	0,06	/	/
20	8	/	/	1,05	0,05	0,96	0,03	1,03	0,05	/	/
20	9	/	/	1,13	0,06	1,00	0,03	1,04	0,05	/	/
20	13	/	/	0,97	0,06	0,90	0,03	0,86	0,04	/	/
20	18	/	/	/	/	0,77	0,02	0,83	0,04	/	/
20	20	/	/	0,85	0,06	/	/	0,75	0,04	/	/
20	25	/	/	0,79	0,05	/	/	0,73	0,04	/	/
20	27	/	/	/	/	0,73	0,02	0,74	0,04	/	/
20	30	/	/	/	/	0,86	0,03	0,85	0,04	/	/
20	35	/	/	/	/	1,03	0,03	1,05	0,06	/	/
20	40	/	/	/	/	1,29	0,04	1,21	0,08	/	/

Table 38: The weighed mean of CF and corresponding standard uncertainty of all results. In this case, RISE measurement at 20 V/m at 18 GHz is excluded from the analysis.

E_{ref} [V/m]	f [GHz]	AF_{wm} [μ]	N [μ]
20	0,01	1,51	0,03
20	0,03	0,97	0,02
20	0,05	0,91	0,01
20	0,07	0,89	0,02
20	0,1	0,88	0,02
20	0,2	0,91	0,02
20	0,3	0,93	0,02
20	0,5	0,92	0,03
20	0,7	0,94	0,03
20	0,9	0,99	0,03
20	1	1,02	0,04
20	1,5	1,02	0,04
20	2	1,08	0,02
20	2,45	1,06	0,02
20	3	1,13	0,03
20	4	1,04	0,02
20	5	1,06	0,02
20	6	1,06	0,02
20	7	1,00	0,02
20	8	0,99	0,02
20	9	1,03	0,02
20	13	0,90	0,02
20	18	0,78	0,02
20	20	0,78	0,03
20	25	0,75	0,03
20	27	0,74	0,02
20	30	0,86	0,02
20	35	1,03	0,03
20	40	1,28	0,03

Table 39: The Degree of Equivalence E_n . In this case, RISE measurement at 20 V/m at 18 GHz is excluded from the analysis.

E_{ref}	f	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CM	IMBiH
		E_n	E_n	E_n	E_n	E_n
[V/m]	[GHz]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
20	0,01	/	0,35	/	-0,35	/
20	0,03	/	0,08	-0,30	0,18	/
20	0,05	/	0,41	-0,44	-0,04	/
20	0,07	/	0,32	-0,30	0,07	/
20	0,1	/	-0,62	-0,06	0,51	/
20	0,2	/	-0,86	0,29	0,36	/
20	0,3	/	-0,47	0,22	0,23	/
20	0,5	/	0,00	-0,63	0,76	/
20	0,7	/	-0,52	0,08	0,47	/
20	0,9	/	-0,97	0,45	0,53	/
20	1	/	-0,18	/	0,18	/
20	1,5	/	-0,03	/	0,03	/
20	2	/	0,76	-0,48	-0,15	/
20	2,45	/	1,03	-0,72	-0,11	/
20	3	/	0,63	0,27	-0,93	/
20	4	/	0,57	-0,59	0,18	/
20	5	/	0,21	-0,21	0,06	/
20	6	/	0,71	-1,14	0,71	/
20	7	/	0,57	-0,91	0,59	/
20	8	/	0,59	-0,84	0,46	/
20	9	/	0,91	-0,79	0,12	/
20	13	/	0,63	0,00	-0,53	/
20	18	/	/	-0,61	0,61	/
20	20	/	0,68	/	-0,68	/
20	25	/	0,51	/	-0,51	/
20	27	/	/	-0,12	0,12	/
20	30	/	/	0,10	-0,10	/
20	35	/	/	-0,14	0,14	/
20	40	/	/	0,50	-0,50	/

Table 40: The x_i and corresponding uncertainty U_i . In this case, RISE measurement at 20 V/m at 18 GHz is excluded from the analysis.

E_{ref}	f	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CMI	IMBiH	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CMI	IMBiH
[V/m]	[GHz]	Δx_i	Δx_i	Δx_i	Δx_i	Δx_i	U_i	U_i	U_i	U_i	U_i
		[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
20	0,01	0	0,017	0	-0,022	0	0	0,049	0	0,061	0
20	0,03	0	0,003	-0,018	0,008	0	0	0,035	0,060	0,044	0
20	0,05	0	0,014	-0,024	-0,002	0	0	0,033	0,056	0,040	0
20	0,07	0	0,030	-0,015	0,002	0	0	0,094	0,051	0,034	0
20	0,1	0	-0,052	-0,003	0,017	0	0	0,083	0,052	0,034	0
20	0,2	0	-0,072	0,016	0,013	0	0	0,084	0,055	0,035	0
20	0,3	0	-0,040	0,010	0,021	0	0	0,084	0,046	0,091	0
20	0,5	0	0,000	-0,031	0,074	0	0	0,087	0,049	0,097	0
20	0,7	0	-0,043	0,004	0,046	0	0	0,083	0,054	0,098	0
20	0,9	0	-0,080	0,026	0,055	0	0	0,083	0,059	0,103	0
20	1	0	-0,014	0	0,015	0	0	0,077	0	0,083	0
20	1,5	0	-0,002	0	0,002	0	0	0,073	0	0,082	0
20	2	0	0,083	-0,018	-0,015	0	0	0,109	0,037	0,106	0
20	2,45	0	0,114	-0,025	-0,012	0	0	0,111	0,035	0,107	0
20	3	0	0,071	0,011	-0,099	0	0	0,113	0,041	0,106	0
20	4	0	0,059	-0,022	0,016	0	0	0,104	0,037	0,089	0
20	5	0	0,021	-0,008	0,005	0	0	0,101	0,039	0,088	0
20	6	0	0,077	-0,041	0,068	0	0	0,108	0,036	0,095	0
20	7	0	0,056	-0,030	0,068	0	0	0,099	0,033	0,114	0
20	8	0	0,059	-0,029	0,043	0	0	0,099	0,034	0,093	0
20	9	0	0,097	-0,028	0,011	0	0	0,107	0,036	0,091	0
20	13	0	0,065	0,000	-0,042	0	0	0,103	0,032	0,079	0
20	18	0	0	-0,013	0,046	0	0	0	0,021	0,075	0
20	20	0	0,066	0	-0,030	0	0	0,097	0	0,045	0
20	25	0	0,045	0	-0,024	0	0	0,089	0	0,046	0
20	27	0	0	-0,003	0,008	0	0	0	0,022	0,063	0
20	30	0	0	0,003	-0,007	0	0	0	0,027	0,070	0
20	35	0	0	-0,004	0,014	0	0	0	0,029	0,099	0
20	40	0	0	0,017	-0,068	0	0	0	0,034	0,137	0

Table 41: The d_i parameter (exclusion of incompatible results). In this case, RISE measurement at 20 V/m at 18 GHz is excluded from the analysis.

E_{ref}	f	SIQ	RISE	TUBITAK	CM	IMBiH
[V/m]	[GHz]	d_i	d_i	d_i	d_i	d_i
		[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]	[/]
20	0,01	/	0,70	/	-0,70	/
20	0,03	/	0,15	-0,59	0,35	/
20	0,05	/	0,81	-0,88	-0,09	/
20	0,07	/	0,64	-0,59	0,13	/
20	0,1	/	-1,25	-0,12	1,01	/
20	0,2	/	-1,71	0,58	0,72	/
20	0,3	/	-0,94	0,43	0,46	/
20	0,5	/	0,00	-1,26	1,53	/
20	0,7	/	-1,04	0,15	0,94	/
20	0,9	/	-1,93	0,89	1,07	/
20	1	/	-0,36	/	0,36	/
20	1,5	/	-0,06	/	0,06	/
20	2	/	1,52	-0,96	-0,29	/
20	2,45	/	2,06	-1,43	-0,23	/
20	3	/	1,26	0,53	-1,86	/
20	4	/	1,14	-1,19	0,36	/
20	5	/	0,41	-0,42	0,12	/
20	6	/	1,42	-2,27	1,42	/
20	7	/	1,13	-1,82	1,19	/
20	8	/	1,19	-1,68	0,92	/
20	9	/	1,81	-1,57	0,24	/
20	13	/	1,26	0,00	-1,06	/
20	18	/	/	-1,22	1,22	/
20	20	/	1,36	/	-1,36	/
20	25	/	1,01	/	-1,01	/
20	27	/	/	-0,24	0,24	/
20	30	/	/	0,20	-0,20	/
20	35	/	/	-0,28	0,28	/
20	40	/	/	0,99	-0,99	/

Table 42: Consistency of results. In this case, RISE measurement at 20 V/m at 18 GHz is excluded from the analysis.

<i>Eref</i>	<i>f</i>	x_{obs}^2	<i>N</i>	<i>chidist</i>
[V/m]	[GHz]	[/]	[/]	[/]
20	0,01	0,49	2	0,48
20	0,03	0,37	3	0,83
20	0,05	0,98	3	0,61
20	0,07	0,60	3	0,74
20	0,1	1,82	3	0,40
20	0,2	2,93	3	0,23
20	0,3	0,92	3	0,63
20	0,5	2,59	3	0,27
20	0,7	1,48	3	0,48
20	0,9	3,89	3	0,14
20	1	0,13	2	0,72
20	1,5	0,00	2	0,95
20	2	2,30	3	0,32
20	2,45	4,30	3	0,12
20	3	4,18	3	0,12
20	4	1,73	3	0,42
20	5	0,22	3	0,89
20	6	5,18	3	0,07
20	7	3,35	3	0,19
20	8	2,87	3	0,24
20	9	3,71	3	0,16
20	13	2,24	3	0,33
20	18	1,50	2	0,22
20	20	1,85	2	0,17
20	25	1,02	2	0,31
20	27	0,06	2	0,81
20	30	0,04	2	0,84
20	35	0,08	2	0,78
20	40	0,99	2	0,32

Fig. 50: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 0.01 GHz.

Fig. 51: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 0.03 GHz.

Fig. 52: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 0.05 GHz.

Fig. 53: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 0.07 GHz.

Fig. 54: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 0.1 GHz.

Fig. 55: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 0.2 GHz.

Fig. 56: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 0.3 GHz.

Fig. 57: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 0.5 GHz.

Fig. 58: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 0.7 GHz

Fig. 59: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 0.9 GHz.

Fig. 60: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 1 GHz.

Fig. 61: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 1.5 GHz.

Fig. 62: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 2 GHz.

Fig. 63: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 2.45 GHz.

Fig. 64: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 3 GHz.

Fig. 65: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 4 GHz.

Fig. 66: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 5 GHz.

Fig. 67: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 6 GHz.

Fig. 68: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 7 GHz.

Fig. 69: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 8 GHz.

Fig. 70: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 9 GHz.

Fig. 71: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 13 GHz.

Fig. 72: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 18 GHz.

Fig. 73: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 20 GHz.

Fig. 74: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 25 GHz.

Fig. 75: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 27 GHz.

Fig. 76: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 30 GHz.

Fig. 77: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 35 GHz.

Fig. 78: Degrees of Equivalence for ETS-Lindgren HI-6053probe at 20 V/m and 40 GHz.

4 Conclusions

In the Deliverable D7, electric and magnetic field probes intercomparison results are shown. Four probes were included in the intercomparison, two for magnetic field and two for electric field. The probes were:

- SIQ
- CMI
- IMBiH
- RISE
- TUBITAK

In all four cases the calibration factor CF needed to be calibrated. Each laboratory could use their own the most convenient field realisation.

The analysis revealed a relatively good agreement among different laboratories:

- **Narda ELT-400:** Unfortunately, only two laboratories participated in this intercomparison (CMI and SIQ) in a frequency range between 0.03 Hz and 10 kHz. Above 10 kHz only CMI performed the measurements. The results are in a good agreement, the minimal χ_{obs} was 0.33 which is well above 0.05 criteria.
- **Narda HF-0191:** Four laboratories participated in this intercomparison (SIQ, RISE, TUBITAK, CMI). The consistency of the results was very good with exception of the measurement at 0.15 A/m at 30 MHz, 50 MHz and 70 MHz. Afterward, RISE's measurements were excluded, and the same analysis was repeated. Afterwards, the results are in a good agreement, the minimal χ_{obs} was 0.36 which is well above 0.05 criteria.
- **Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300:** Five laboratories participated in this intercomparison (SIQ, RISE, TUBITAK, CMI, IMBiH). The results are in a good agreement, the minimal χ_{obs} was 0.24 which is well above 0.05 criteria. The most problematic measuring point was at 50 V/m and 23 kHz (in this case, RISE deviates the most). However, no exclusion of the results was necessary.
- **ETS-Lindgren HI-6053:** Three laboratories participated in the measurements (RISE, TUBITAK, CMI). The consistency of the results was very good with exception of the measurement at 20 V/m at 18 GHz. The highest absolute d_i had RISE therefore this measuring point from RISE was excluded from the intercomparison. Then the same analysis was repeated. The minimal χ_{obs} was 0.07 (TUBITAK at 20 V/m and 6 GHz) therefore no further exclusion of the results was necessary.

SIQ report

The measurements were performed by Marko Berginc from SIQ. Three probes have been measured on the dates listed below:

- Narda ELT-400: 31.7.2025
- Wandel & Goltermann EFA 300: 29.7.2025
- Narda HF-0191: 22.10.2025

The participant information's are gathered in Table 1.

Table 1: Participant information

Institute Name	SIQ
Contact Person	Marko Berginc
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e-mail	marko.berginc@siq.si
Address	SIQ Mašera-Spasičeva ulica 10 1000 Ljubljana Slovenia

OTHER DATA

- Temperature: (23±2) °C
- Relative Humidity: (50±20) %
- Measurement date: 31.7.2025, 29.7.2025 and 22.10.2025

DESCRIPTION OF MEASUREMENT METHOD

Three different setups were used for probe calibration, Helmholtz coil for Narda ELT-400, parallel plate capacitor for Wandel&Goltermann EFA 300 probe and TEM cell for Narda HF-0191 probe.

Narda ELT-400

The measuring setup based on Helmholtz coil is shown in Fig. 1. The function generator is connected to the input of the audio amplifier. The output of the audio amplifier is connected to the Ampere-meter and Helmholtz coil which are connected in series. The radius of the Helmholtz coil and the distance between the coils are 54.2 cm. The magnetic field density B has been calculated using Eq. 1 and the corresponding coil factor CF using Eq. 2.

$$B_s = \frac{\mu_0 \cdot N \cdot I}{r \cdot (1,25)^{3/2}} \quad (1)$$

$$B_s = CF \cdot B_x \quad (2)$$

The uncertainty contributions are specification, resolution and type-A of the A-meter measurement, uncertainty due to the radius of the Helmholtz coil, homogeneity of the magnetic field density and the deviation of the magnetic field density when the probe was inserted in the Helmholtz coil.

Fig. 1: Calibration setup for generating magnetic field with Helmholtz coil

Wandel & Goltermann EFA 300

The measuring setup based on parallel plate capacitor is shown in Fig. 2. Calibrator was directly connected to the plates of parallel plate capacitor. The distance between the plates was 48.0 cm. Electric field density E_s was calculated using Eq. 3 while the calibration factor CF was calculated using Eq. 4. Uncertainty contributions were specification of the calibrator, uncertainty of the distance between the electrodes, uncertainty due to the inhomogeneity of the electric field, uncertainty due to the deviation of the electric field when the probe was inserted in a parallel plate capacitor and uncertainty due to the deviation of the electric field when the probe holder was inserted in a parallel plate capacitor.

Fig. 2: Calibration setup for generating electric field E_s with parallel plate capacitor

$$E_s = \frac{V_s}{d} \quad (3)$$

$$E_s = CF \cdot E_x \quad (4)$$

Narda HF-0191

The measuring setup based on TEM cell (septum distance 10 cm) is shown in Fig. 3. The signal generator is connected to the RF amplifier. The output of the amplifier is connected to the Port 1 of the TEM cell. Port 2 of the TEM cell is connected to the input of the attenuator while a RF power sensor is connected to the output of the attenuator. The magnetic field strength in a TEM cell was calculated using Eq. 5, where the P denotes the power in a TEM cell (roughly the power measured by the power sensor multiplied by the attenuation of the attenuator), d is the septum distance and Z_0 is impedance of free space (roughly 377Ω). The CF is calculated using Eq. 6. Uncertainty contributions includes the uncertainty of power measurements (typical A, resolution, specification, CF of the power sensor and corresponding uncertainty, uncertainty of

attenuator, mismatch between power sensor and attenuator with corresponding uncertainty, *etc.*), uncertainty associated to the septum distance, uncertainty due to the deviation of the magnetic field strength when the probe was inserted in a TEM cell, uncertainty due to the deviation of the magnetic field strength when the probe holder was inserted in a parallel plate capacitor and uncertainty due to inhomogeneity of the magnetic field strength.

Fig. 3: Calibration setup for generating magnetic field strength in TEM cell

$$H_s = \frac{\sqrt{P \cdot Z}}{d \cdot Z_0} \quad (5)$$

$$H_s = CF \cdot H_x \quad (6)$$

EQUIPMENT

The equipment that was used during the calibration is listed in Tables 2-4.

Table 2: Standards used in measurements of Narda ELT-400 probe.

Name of Equipment	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No.
Multimeter	Fluke	8508A	876148875
Laser distance meter	Fluke	424D	54360009
Function generator	Auxiliary equipment		
Audio amplifier			
Helmholtz coil			

Table 3: Standards used in measurements of Wandel&Goltermann EFA 300 probe.

Name of Equipment	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No.
Calibrator	Fluke	5730A	876148875
Laser distance meter	Fluke	424D	54360009
Parallel plate capacitor	Auxiliary equipment		

Table 4: Standards used in measurements of Narda HF-0191 probe.

Name of Equipment	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No.
Power sensor	R&S	NRV-Z51	100818
Power meter	R&S	URV 55	844864/005
Attenuator	Bird	1000A-QFFN-30	0841
Laser distance meter	Fluke	424D	54360009
Signal generator	Auxiliary equipment		
RF amplifier			
TEM cell			

DESCRIPTION OF TRACEABILITY

Traceability of the standard is provided in Table 5.

Table 5: Traceability of standards used for intercomparison

Name of Equipment	Manufacturer, model type	Traceability
Multimeter	Fluke, 8508A, s.n. 876148875	In house calibration, traceability to PTB
Laser distance meter	Fluke, 424D, s.n. 54360009	Calibration at SIJ Ravne
Calibrator	Fluke, 5730A, s.n. 876148875	In house calibration, traceability to PTB
Power sensor	R&S, NRV-Z51, s.n. 100818	In house calibration, traceability to Metas
Power meter	R&S, URV 55, s.n. 844864/005	In house calibration, traceability to PTB
Attenuator	Bird, 1000A-QFFN-30, s.n. 0841	In house calibration, traceability to Metas

UNCERTAINTY BUDGET EXAMPLE FOR EACH FIELD REALIZATION

The uncertainty budget calculation example low-frequency magnetic field density and low-frequency electric field strength are shown in Tables 6 and 7.

Table 6: An example of low-frequency magnetic field probe (Narda ELT-400) uncertainty calculation is given for calibration at nominal field strength $B_s = 30 \mu\text{T}$ at $f = 1 \text{ kHz}$. Fluke 8508A multimeter was used to measure the current. Five readings of DUT probe were measured and noted.

Mathematical model of measurement:

Is_mean	503,4 mA	$\Delta B_z = (B_{z,x} + k_{r,x}) - \frac{\mu_0 \cdot (N + k_N) \cdot (I + k_{I,spec} + k_{I,res})}{(r + k_r) \cdot (1,25)^{3/2}} + k_{B,hom} + k_{B,hold} + k_{B,probe} + k_{B,bias}$
Is_div	0,15 mA	
Bx,mean	30,00 μT	
Bx,max - Bx,mins	0,06 μT	

Quantity X_i	Estimate x_i	Standard uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Probability distribution	Div.	Sensitivity coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u_i(y)$	Effective degr. Of freedom v_i
Bx	30,00 μT	0,017 μT	rectangular	1,73	1 /	0,017 μT	4
$k_{r,x}$	0 μT	0,003 μT	rectangular	1,73	1 /	0,0029 μT	1E+99
I	0,503 A	0,00015 A	normal	1	-60 $\mu\text{T/A}$	-0,009 μT	4
$k_{I,spec}$	0,0 A	0,00030 A	rectangular	1,73	-60 $\mu\text{T/A}$	-0,018 μT	1E+99
$k_{I,res}$	0,0 A	0,000000 A	rectangular	1,73	-60 $\mu\text{T/A}$	0,0000 μT	1E+99
N	36 /	0 /	rectangular	1,73	-0,8 μT	0 μT	1E+99
r	0,542 m	0,00029 m	normal	1	55 $\mu\text{T/m}$	0,016 μT	4
k_{hom}	0 μT	0,3 μT	normal	1	1 /	0,3 μT	1E+99
k_{hold}	0 μT	0 μT	normal	1	1 /	0 μT	1E+99
k_{probe}	0 μT	0,15 μT	normal	1	1 /	0,15 μT	1E+99
k_{bias}	0 μT	0,0 μT	normal	1	1 /	0 μT	1E+99
ΔB_z	-0,1 μT	Calculated uncertainty:				0,3 μT	316678
		Expanded uncertainty of measurement:				0,7 μT	
		Expanded relative uncertainty of measurement:				2,2 %	

Table 7: Uncertainty calculation example of low-frequency electric field probe (Wandel&Goltermann EFA 300) that is measured at 2133 V/m and 50 Hz. Calibrator Fluke 5730A was used as a voltage source. Five readings of probe were measured and noted.

Mathematical model of measurement:

Ex_min	2133,7 V/m	$\Delta E_z = (E_{z,x} + k_{r,x}) - \frac{V_s + k_{U,spec}}{d + k_d} + k_{E,hom} + k_{E,hold} + k_{E,probe}$
Ex_max	2133,8 V/m	

Quantity X_i	Estimate x_i	Standard uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Probability distribution	Div.	Sensitivity coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u_i(y)$	Effective degr. Of freedom v_i
Vs	1000 V	0,000 V	rectangular	1,73	-2,08 1/m	0 V/m	1E+99
$k_{U,spec}$	0 V	0,179 V	rectangular	1,73	-2,08 1/m	-0,373 V/m	1E+99
d	0,4801 m	0 m	normal	1	-4338 V/m ²	0 V/m	1E+99
k_d	0 m	0,00027 m	normal	1	-4338 V/m ²	-1,2 V/m	10
Ex	2133,75 V/m	0,03 V/m	rectangular	1,73	1 /	0,03 V/m	4
$k_{r,x}$	0 V/m	0,03 V/m	rectangular	1,73	1 /	0,03 V/m	1E+99
$k_{E,hom}$	0 V/m	10,41 V/m	normal	1	1 /	10,41 V/m	1E+99
$k_{E,hold}$	0 V/m	20,8 V/m	normal	1	1 /	20,8 V/m	1E+99
$k_{E,probe}$	0 V/m	10,4 V/m	normal	1	1 /	10,4 V/m	1E+99
ΔE	51,0 V/m	Calculated uncertainty:				26 V/m	2,E+06
		Expanded uncertainty of measurement:				51 V/m	
		Expanded relative uncertainty of measurement:				2,45 %	

MEASUREMENT RESULTS

The measurements results are shown in Tables 8-10. The ambient temperature and relative humidity during the calibration were $23\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $50\% \pm 20\%$, respectively.

Table 8: Measurement results for Narda ELT-400 probe

Frequency (kHz)	B_s (μT)	CF (dB)	$Unc. (k=2)$ (dB)
0.03	10	0.21	0.19
0.055	10	0.12	0.19
0.1	10	0.09	0.19
1	10	0.07	0.19
3	10	0.09	0.19
5	6	0.08	0.19
10	3	0.04	0.19

Table 9: Measurement results for Wandel&Goltermann EFA 300 probe

Frequency (kHz)	E_s (V/m)	CF (dB)	$Unc. (k=2)$ (dB)
0.01	50	0.07	0.24
0.02	50	-0.07	0.24
0.02	457	0.01	0.24
0.05	100	-0.05	0.24
0.05	1001	0.01	0.24
0.05	2002	0.01	0.24
0.1	50	-0.09	0.24
0.4	50	-0.10	0.24
1	50	-0.10	0.24
1	1001	-0.03	0.24
5	50	-0.11	0.24
7	50	-0.09	0.24
10	50	-0.04	0.24
10	1001	-0.13	0.24
15	50	0.08	0.24
20	50	0.27	0.24
23	50	0.46	0.24
25	50	0.68	0.24
27	50	1.07	0.24
30	50	2.15	0.24
30	500	2.15	0.24

Table 10: Measurement results for Narda HF-0191 probe

Frequency (MHz)	H_s (A/m)	CF (dB)	$Unc. (k=2)$ (dB)
30	0.150	0.92	0.51
50	0.151	-0.33	0.51
70	0.150	-0.54	0.51
100	0.150	-0.51	0.51
200	0.150	-0.18	0.51
300	0.151	-0.02	0.99
400	0.151	-0.01	0.99
500	0.151	-0.32	0.99
600	0.151	-0.61	0.99
700	0.151	-0.94	0.99
800	0.151	-0.63	1.00

Field probe comparison report, RISE

1. Participant Information

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2. Measurement Date

Measurement Dates2025-08-17..... –2022-08-21.....
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 C2 - Internal

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3. Environmental Condition

Temperature (°C)	22.5 (2025-08-17) / 23.2 (2025-08-21)
Relative Humidity (%rh)	34.3 (2025-08-17) / 39.5 (2025-08-21)

4. References Used In Measurement

Name of Equipment	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No
TEM-cell	RISE	-	RISE inv. Nr: 503897
Signal Generator	Rohde&Schwarz	SMB100	1422.1000K02-104671-iK
Power amplifier	Rohde & Schwarz	BBA150	2065.9470.90-105228-iB
Power meter	Boonton	4242RF	14793
Power sensor1	Boonton	51015-EF	35916
Power sensor2	Boonton	51015-EF	35917
Termination	Inmet	TN020F-300W	RISE inv. Nr: KWP01299
Temperature meter	Testo	615	RISE inv. Nr: 503498
Transfer field probe	PTB	-	14564
u-TEM cell	Schaffner	-	RISE inv. Nr: 503154
Standard Gain Horn	Flann	06240	55
Standard Gain Horn	Flann	08240	119
Standard Gain Horn	Flann	10240	96
Standard Gain Horn	Flann	12240	148478
Standard Gain Horn	Flann	14240	146

Standard Gain Horn	Flann	16240	579
Standard Gain Horn	Flann	18240	477
Standard Gain Horn	Flann	20240	275170
Standard Gain Horn	Flann	22240	274184
Power meter	Boonton	PMX40	18147
Power sensor	Boonton	RTP5540	12160
Signal Generator	Rohde & Schwarz	SMR 40	832034/0016
Power amplifier	Teseq	CBA1G-600D	1102593
Power amplifier	Amplifier Research	AR20S4G18	0347843
Power amplifier	Amplifier Research	AR100S1G6	0346919
Power amplifier	Axend	AXDA2640-40	S21112601
Power amplifier	Bonn Elektronik	BLMA 1826-20	211540

5. Measurement Procedure

Different methods were used depending on frequency range and which type of field probe that were to be calibrated. Table 5.1 gives a summary of which method that was used for each probe and/or frequency range.

Field probe	Frequency range	Field type	Method used	Chapter
Narda HF-0191	30M-80M	H	TEM-cell	§5.1
W&A EFA-300	10k-30k	E	TEM-cell	§5.2
ETS-Lindgren HI-6053	10M-50M	E	TEM-cell	§5.2
	70M-1G	E	Transfer standard in Anechoic Chamber	§ 5.3
	1G-25G	E	Horn antenna in Anechoic Chamber	§5.4

Table 5.1: Methods used

5.1 H-field using a TEM-cell

The method generates a traceable electromagnetic field inside a TEM-cell. The field is known from calculations and the test object is placed in this known field. The following setup is used:

Figure1: Setup TEM-cell calibration

The field strength in the TEM-cell is calculated as:

$$B_{actual} = Z_L^{1/2} * Z_0^{-1} * \left(P_{FWD} \frac{P_2}{P_1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} T_{TEM}^{\frac{1}{4}} * d^{-1} * \delta(x, y, z)^1 * corr \quad (5.1a)$$

where:

Z_L =Characteristic impedance of the TEM-cell.

Z_0 =Free space impedance.

P_{FWD} =Power output from the amplifier (measured at the power forward on the directional coupler), absolute power measurement.

P_1 =Forward power of the directional coupler, relative power measurement.

P_2 =Power after directional coupler and cable, relative power measurement.

T_{TEM} =Loss through TEM-cell, relative power measurement.

d =Distance between centre conductor and floor.

$\delta(x, y, z)$: =Uncertainty from location errors in x, y and z-directions.

corr: =Correction factor caused by impedance mismatch of TEM cell.

The power is measured with a power meter calibrated with traceability to other national measurement institutes (last calibration at METAS, Switzerland). The impedance (S11) is measured using a network analyzer calibrated with traceability to the manufacturer Rohde & Schwarz, using a calibration kit with traceability to other national measurement institutes (last calibration at METAS, Switzerland). The distance is measured with a laser rangefinder calibrated at RISE, with the traceability to the RISE NMI department for length.

5.2 E-field using a TEM-cell

The method generates a traceable electromagnetic field inside a TEM-cell. The field is known from calculations and the test object is placed in this known field. The following setup is used:

Figure2: Setup TEM-cell calibration

The field strength in the TEM-cell is calculated as:

$$E_{actual} = Z_L^{1/2} * \left(P_{FWD} \frac{P_2}{P_1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} T_{TEM}^{\frac{1}{4}} * d^{-1} * \delta(x, y, z)^1 * corr \quad (5.2a)$$

where:

Z_L =Characteristic impedance of the TEM-cell.

P_{FWD} =Power output from the amplifier (measured at the power forward on the directional coupler), absolute power measurement.

P_1 =Forward power of the directional coupler, relative power measurement.

P_2 =Power after directional coupler and cable, relative power measurement.

T_{TEM} =Loss through TEM-cell, relative power measurement.

d =Distance between centre conductor and floor.

$\delta(x, y, z)$: =Uncertainty from location errors in x, y and z-directions.

$corr$: =Correction factor caused by impedance mismatch of TEM cell.

The power is measured with a power meter calibrated with traceability to other national measurement institutes (last calibration at METAS, Switzerland). The impedance (S11) is measured using a network analyzer calibrated with traceability to the manufacturer Rohde & Schwarz, using a calibration kit with traceability to other national measurement institutes (last calibration at METAS, Switzerland).. The distance is measured with a laser rangefinder calibrated at RISE, with the traceability to the RISE NMI department for length.

5.3 Transfer probe calibration

The calibration method is based on a RISE-method which generates a traceable electromagnetic field inside a μ TEM-cell. In this cell a transfer field probe is calibrated. The calibration of the test object is performed in an anechoic chamber in front of a transmitting antenna, where the readout from the test object is compared of the reference level indicated by the transfer field probe.

The calibration factor is defined as:

$$k = \frac{E_{ref,DUT}}{E_{DUT}} \quad (5.3a)$$

where $E_{ref,DUT}$ is the reference level and E_{DUT} is the test object reading. The calibration factor can be expanded as:

$$k = (c \cdot E_T)^1 \cdot (E_{DUT})^{-1} \cdot (P_T)^{-1/2} \cdot (P_{DUT})^{1/2} \cdot (\Delta G)^{1/2} \cdot \Delta R \quad (5.3b)$$

Where:

k = Test object calibration factor.

c = Transfer probe calibration factor, from internal RISE method 2896B [1].

E_T = Reading from transfer probe.

P_{DUT} = Directional coupler forward power, relative power measurement [5].

P_T = Directional coupler forward power, relative power measurement [5].

ΔG = ratio between 1) the gain when the transfer probe is measured and 2) gain when the test object is measured (angular errors).

ΔR = distance ratio. The calibration object and transfer probe cannot be located at exactly same point in space.

Traceability requires that the following parameters can be measured in a traceable way:

- Transfer field probe calibration factor. It is calibrated principally in the same way as in chapter 5.2, with the same sources for traceability.
- Power - measured with a power meter calibrated with traceability to national measurement institutes (last time to Metas, Switzerland).
- Positioning of the transfer field probe and test subject in anechoic chamber. Positioning is relative and is performed with a laser pointer (calibration not required).

5.4 E-field probe calibrations using horn antennas

The calibration factor is defined as:

$$c = \frac{E_{ref}}{E_{DUT}} \quad (5.4a)$$

where E_{ref} is the reference level of the electric field, and E_{DUT} is the test object readout of the same field.

Before any calibration, the system is calibrated, see Figure 3.

Figure3: Setup System calibration

where

G = The gain of the reference antenna

P_{FWD} = Forward power at directional coupler

P_1, P_2 = Power measurements at system calibration (see Fig. 3)

R = Distance from antenna aperture to test object

The setup used:

Figure 4: Test setup - Tx part.

AC = Anechoic Chamber.

the electric field at the test object can be calculated as:

$$E_{ref} = \frac{\sqrt{30G}}{R} \cdot \sqrt{P_{FWD} \frac{P_2}{P_1}} \quad (5.4b)$$

G = The gain of the reference antenna

P_{FWD} = Forward power at directional coupler

P_1, P_2 = Power measurements at system calibration (see Fig. 3)

R = Distance from antenna aperture to test object

Combining (5.4a) with (5.4b) and adding a factor for mismatch error, will result in the expression (5.4c) for the calibration factor.

$$c = \sqrt{30} \cdot G_{ref}^{0.5} \left(P_{FWD} \frac{P_2}{P_1} \right)^{0.5} E_{DUT}^{-1} (1 - |S_{11}|^2)^{0.5} R^{-1} \frac{|1 - \Gamma_e \Gamma_p|}{|1 - \Gamma_e \Gamma_a|} \quad (5.4c)$$

where:

Γ_e = Effective reflection coefficient of directional coupler and cable

Γ_p = Reflection coefficient of power meter

Γ_a = Reflection coefficient of antenna

From (5.4c) it is to be seen that the traceability requires that the power, the reference antenna gain, and the test object's position can be determined in a traceable way. The power is measured with 1) a power meter calibrated with traceability to a national measurement institute (last time at Metas Switzerland) up to 18 GHz, and 2) a power meter calibrated at RISE department HF for frequencies over 18 GHz. The gain of the reference antennas are calibrated internally at RISE NMI department for HF. The positioning is performed with a laser rangefinder. The laser range finder is calibrated at RISE NMI department for length.

6. Measurement Results

Field probe	Frequency	Level for Field Measurements	Correction Factor (dB)	Measurement Uncertainty (dB) (k=2)
Narda HF-0191	30 MHz	0.1467 (A/m)	0.041	0.42
	50 MHz	0.1411 (A/m)	-1.820	0.42
	70 MHz	0.1367 (A/m)	-1.477	0.42
	80 MHz	0.1396 (A/m)	-0.738	0.42
EFA-300	10 kHz	49.86 (V/m)	-0.087	0.42
	15 kHz	50.14 (V/m)	-0.265	0.42
	20 kHz	49.91 (V/m)	-0.087	0.42
	23 kHz	49.68 (V/m)	0.086	0.42
	25 kHz	49.63 (V/m)	0.341	0.42
	27 kHz	49.91 (V/m)	0.749	0.42
	30 kHz	49.97 (V/m)	1.798	0.42
HI-6053	10 MHz	19.74 (V/m)	3.694	0.42
	30 MHz	19.70 (V/m)	-0.265	0.42
	50 MHz	19.05 (V/m)	-0.724	0.42
	70 MHz	19.44 (V/m)	-0.724	0.95
	100 MHz	20.20 (V/m)	-1.618	0.95
	200 MHz	19.20 (V/m)	-1.514	0.95
	300 MHz	19.69 (V/m)	-1.012	0.95
	500 MHz	19.30 (V/m)	-0.724	0.95
	700 MHz	19.38 (V/m)	-0.915	0.95
	900 MHz	19.18 (V/m)	-0.819	0.95
	1000 MHz	19.80 (V/m)	0.086	0.95
	1500 MHz	20.21 (V/m)	0.172	0.9

	2000 MHz	20.32 (V/m)	1.289	0.9
	2450 MHz	20.19 (V/m)	1.364	0.9
	3000 MHz	20.12 (V/m)	1.584	0.9
	4000 MHz	19.73 (V/m)	0.828	0.9
	5000 MHz	20.23 (V/m)	0.668	0.9
	6000 MHz	19.97 (V/m)	1.138	0.9
	7000 MHz	19.96 (V/m)	0.506	0.9
	8000 MHz	19.95 (V/m)	0.424	0.9
	9000 MHz	19.91 (V/m)	1.062	0.9
	13000 MHz	19.95 (V/m)	-0.265	1.0
	18000 MHz	20.07 (V/m)	-0.724	1.0
	20000 MHz	20.10 (V/m)	-1.454	1.2
	25000 MHz	20.05 (V/m)	-2.006	1.2

7. Detailed Uncertainty Budget

7.1 H-field using a TEM-cell

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of Hz						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
Z _L : Characteristic impedance of the TEM-cell	A	0.08639	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	0.02512
Z ₀ : Free space impedance	A	0	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	0
P _{FWD} : Power output from the amplifier	A	0.11486	Normal	1	$\frac{1}{2}$	0.05781
P ₁ : Forward power of the directional coupler	A	0.10470	Normal	1	$\frac{1}{2}$	0.05266
P ₂ : Power after directional coupler and cable	A	0.10470	Normal	1	$\frac{1}{2}$	0.05266
T _{TEM} : Loss through TEM-cell	A	0.12871	Normal	1	$\frac{1}{4}$	0.03254
d: Distance between centre conductor and floor	A	0.02251	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.01301
$\delta(x, y, z)$: Uncertainty from location errors	A	0.29373	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.17200
<i>Corr</i> : Impedance mismatch of TEM cell	A	0.08639	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.05009
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0.41059

Table 7.1: Uncertainty for H-field using a TEM-cell

7.2 E-field using a TEM-cell

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of Hz						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
Z _L : Characteristic impedance of the TEM-cell	A	0.08639	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	0.02512
P _{FWD} : Power output from the amplifier	A	0.11486	Normal	1	$\frac{1}{2}$	0.05781

P ₁ : Forward power of the directional coupler	A	0.10470	Normal	1	½	0.05266
P ₂ : Power after directional coupler and cable	A	0.10470	Normal	1	½	0.05266
T _{TEM} : Loss through TEM-cell	A	0.12871	Normal	1	¼	0.03254
d: Distance between centre conductor and floor	A	0.02251	Rectangular	√3	1	0.01301
δ(x, y, z) : Uncertainty from location errors	A	0.29373	Rectangular	√3	1	0.17200
Corr : Impedance mismatch of TEM cell	A	0.08639	Rectangular	√3	1	0.05009
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0.41059

Table 7.2: Uncertainty for E-field using a TEM-cell

7.3 E-field using a Transfer probe standard

Source of uncertainty	Value	Type of distribution	Divisor	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution
uTEM	0.0551	Normal	2	1.00	0.0276
Transferprobe	0.0174	Normal	2	1.00	0.0087
Rel.Power P _{dut}	0.0123	Normal	2	0.50	0.0031
Rel. Power TP	0.0123	Normal	2	0.50	0.0031
Placement x,y	0.0386	Normal	2	1.00	0.0193
Placement z	0.0232	Normal	2	1.00	0.0116
Harmonics TP	0.024	U-shape	1.414	1.00	0.0170
Harmonics DUT	0.024	U-shape	1.414	1.00	0.0170
Repeatability TP	0.0419	Normal	2	1.00	0.0210
Repeatability E _{dut}	0.025	Normal	2	1.00	0.0125
Site imperfections	0.025	Normal	1	1	0.0250
Total Uncertainty (k=2) dB					0.9496

Table 7.3: Uncertainty for E-field using a transfer standard.

7.4 E-field using horn antennas

Source of uncertainty	Value	Divisor	Type of distribution	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution
Abs. Power	0.0636	2.000	Normal	0.50	0.0159
Rel. Power (P ₂)	0.0636	2.000	Normal	0.50	0.0159

Rel. Power (P1)	0.0636	2.000	Normal	0.50	0.0159
Ref. Gain	0.1	1.000	Normal	0.50	0.0500
Far field	0.077	1.732	Rectangular	1.00	0.0445
Mismatch ea	0.0145	1.414	U-shape	1.00	0.0103
Mismatch ep	0.0175	1.414	U-shape	1.00	0.0124
Drift	0.0258	1.732	Rectangular	1.00	0.0105
Site imperfections	0.071519	1.000	Normal	1.00	0.0715
Total Uncertainty (k=2) dB					0.8599

Table 7.6A: Measurement uncertainty 1-12 GHz

Source of uncertainty	Value	Divisor	Type of distribution	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution
Abs. Power	0.0965	2.000	Normal	0.50	0.0394
Rel. Power (P2)	0.0636	2.000	Normal	0.50	0.0260
Rel. Power (P1)	0.0636	2.000	Normal	0.50	0.0260
Ref. Gain	0.1	1.000	Normal	0.50	0.0500
Far field	0.077	1.732	Rectangular	1.00	0.0445
Mismatch ea	0.0145	1.414	U-shape	1.00	0.0103
Mismatch ep	0.0175	1.414	U-shape	1.00	0.0124
Drift	0.0258	1.732	Rectangular	1.00	0.0105
Site imperfections	0.071519	1.000	Normal	1.00	0.0715
Total Uncertainty (k=2) dB					0.9075

Table 7.6B: Measurement uncertainty 13-18 GHz

Source of uncertainty	Value	Divisor	Type of distribution	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution
Abs. Power	0.1615	2.000	Normal	0.50	0.0659
Rel. Power (P2)	0.1	2.000	Normal	0.50	0.0408
Rel. Power (P1)	0.1	2.000	Normal	0.50	0.0408
Ref. Gain	0.1	1.000	Normal	0.50	0.0500
Far field	0.077	1.732	Rectangular	1.00	0.0445
Mismatch ea	0.0145	1.414	U-shape	1.00	0.0103
Mismatch ep	0.0175	1.414	U-shape	1.00	0.0124
Drift	0.0258	1.732	Rectangular	1.00	0.0105
Site imperfections	0.071519	1.000	Normal	1.00	0.0715
Total Uncertainty (k=2) dB					1.1077

Table 7.6C: Measurement uncertainty 18.1-25 GHz

RISE Research Institutes of Sweden AB
Vehicles and Automation - Wireless Communication

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Examined by

Mats Cedheim

Supplementary comparison report on electric/magnetic field strength measurements

Development of RF and Microwave Metrology Capability II (22RPT04 RF&Microwave2)

1. Participant Information

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2. Measurement Date

Measurement Dates	18.11.2025 – 18.12.2025
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3. Environmental Condition

Temperature (°C)	22 ± 2
Relative Humidity (%rh)	45 ± 10

4. References Used In Measurement

Name of Equipment	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No
Power Sensor	Keysight Technologies	U8481A	MY60290002
Power Sensor	Rohde & Schwarz	NRP-Z55	130099
Power Sensor	Rohde & Schwarz	NRP-Z55	130100
Power Sensor	Rohde & Schwarz	NRP-Z55	130096
Power Meter	Keysight Technologies	N1914A	MY60270004
Power Meter	Rohde & Schwarz	NRP2	101630
Horn Antenna	A.H. Systems	SAS-584	141
Horn Antenna	A.H. Systems	SAS-583	138
Horn Antenna	A.H. Systems	SAS-581	147
Horn Antenna	A.H. Systems	SAS-582	140
Horn Antenna	A-INFO	JTXTLB-90-15-C-NF	J2022090813004
Horn Antenna	A-INFO	JTXTLB-62-15-C-NF	J2021090814002
Horn Antenna	Pasternack	PE9850-20	003
Horn Antenna	Schwarzbeck	BBHA 9120 E	9120E-593
Signal Generator	Agilent Technologies	E8257C	US42340292
Signal Generator	IFR Inc.	2023A	202304/699
Signal Generator	Agilent Technologies	33120A	MY40023817

Name of Equipment	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No
Attenuator	AEROFLEX	58-40-34	QC998
Directional Coupler	ATM Inc.	PNR 62-303A-30F-30R-6-6	K412407z-01
Directional Coupler	ATM Inc.	PNR 187-303A-40F-40R-2-2	K411707z-01
Directional Coupler	ATM Inc.	PNR 284-303A-40F-40R-2-2	K411507z-01
Directional Coupler	ATM Inc.	PNR 137-303A-40F-40R-2-2	K411907z-01
Directional Coupler	ATM Inc.	PNR 28-303A-40F-40R-6-6	K412707z-01
Directional Coupler	ATM Inc.	PNR 90-303A-40F-40R-6-6	K412107z-01
Directional Coupler	ATM Inc.	PNR 430-303A-40F-40R-2-2	K411307z-01
Directional Coupler	Bonn Elektronik	BDC 0810-40/500	097574
AC High Voltage Probe	Fluke	80K-6	004
Multimeter	Fluke	287	21110005

5. Measurement Procedure

5.1. HF-0191 Measurements:

The measurements were performed at the center of TEM cell of which theoretical magnetic field strength values are known at the frequency range of 30 MHz - 400 MHz (Figure 1) and in the fully anechoic chamber of which theoretical magnetic field strength values are known at the frequency range of 500 MHz - 1000 MHz. During the fully anechoic chamber measurement process, the magnetic field probe was located directly opposite the vertically polarized horn antenna (Figure 2). The measurements were performed according to the IEEE Std 1309 calculated field method. The measurement process was carried out by reading the total magnetic field strength on the magnetic field probe. Also the measurements were performed under the continuous wave.

The theoretical magnetic field strength values were calculated for TEM cell measurements using the formula below,

$$H = \frac{\sqrt{P \cdot Z_0}}{b \cdot \eta_0}$$

Where;

H is the theoretical RMS magnetic field strength (A/m)

P is the power at the output of the TEM cell (W)

Z_0 is the real part of the characteristic impedance of the TEM cell (Ohm)

b is the distance from the upper wall to the center plate of TEM cell (m)

η_0 is impedance of the free space (Ohm)

Figure 1. TEM cell measurement setup

The theoretical magnetic field strength values were calculated for fully anechoic chamber measurements using the formula below,

$$H = \sqrt{\frac{\eta \cdot P_{net} \cdot g}{4 \cdot \pi \cdot d^2}} / \eta_0$$

Where;

H is the theoretical RMS magnetic field strength(A/m)

η is intrinsic impedance (Ohm)

P_{net} is the net input power to the transmitting antenna (W)

g is gain of the transmitting antenna (dBi)

d is distance from the transmitting antenna to the receiving point (m)

η_0 is impedance of the free space (Ohm)

Figure 2. Fully anechoic chamber measurement setup

During the measurements, the settings of the NBM 550 are given Table 1.

Table 1. Settings of the NBM 550

Display	Apply Cor. Freq.
Actual	OFF

5.2. EFA-300, BN2245/90.31 Measurements:

The measurements were performed at the center of TEM cell and 50 Hz high level electric field system (Parallel plates) of which theoretical electric field strength values are known according to the calculated field method (Figure 3 and Figure 4). The measurement process was carried out by reading the total electric field strength on the electric field probe. Also the measurements were performed under the continuous wave.

The theoretical electric field strength values were calculated for TEM cell measurements using the formula below.

$$E = \frac{\sqrt{P \cdot Z_0}}{b}$$

E is the theoretical RMS electric field strength (V/m)

P is the power at the output of the TEM cell (W)

Z₀ is the real part of the characteristic impedance of the TEM cell (Ohm)

b is the distance from the upper wall to the center plate of TEM cell (m)

The theoretical electric field strength values were calculated for 50 Hz high level electric field system (Parallel plates) measurements using the formula below. The measurements were carried out at 100 V/m, 1000 V/m and 2000 V/m field strength levels.

$$E = \frac{V}{d}$$

E is the theoretical RMS electric field strength (V/m)

V is the voltage level between the plates (V)

d is the distance between plates (m)

During the calibration, the settings of the EFA-300, BN2245 are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Settings of the EFA-300, BN-2245

Measurement Mode	Measurement range	Filter	Detection mode	Display mode	Channel
Field Strength	Auto	5 Hz – 32 kHz	RMS	Live	Isotropic

Figure 3. Example TEM cell measurement setup

Figure 4. 50 Hz high level electric field system measurement setup

5.3. HI-6053 Measurements:

The measurements were performed at the center of TEM cell of which theoretical electric field strength values are known at the frequency range of 10 MHz - 300 MHz (Figure 5) and in the fully anechoic chamber of which theoretical electric field strength values are known at the frequency range of 500 MHz - 40 GHz. During the fully anechoic chamber measurement process, the electric field probe was located directly opposite the vertically polarized horn antenna (Figure 6). The measurements were performed according to the IEEE Std 1309 calculated field method. The measurement process was carried out by reading the total electric field strength on the electric field probe. Also the measurements were performed under the continuous wave.

The theoretical electric field strength values were calculated for TEM cell measurements using the formula below,

$$E = \frac{\sqrt{P \cdot Z_0}}{b}$$

Where;

E is the theoretical RMS electric field strength (V/m)

P is the power at the output of the TEM cell (W)

Z_0 is the real part of the characteristic impedance of the TEM cell (Ohm)

b is the distance from the upper wall to the center plate of TEM cell (m)

Figure 5. TEM cell measurement setup

The theoretical electric field strength values were calculated for fully anechoic chamber measurements using the formula below,

$$E = \sqrt{\frac{\eta \cdot P_{net} \cdot g}{4 \cdot \pi \cdot d^2}}$$

Where;

E is the theoretical RMS electric field strength (V/m)

η is intrinsic impedance (Ohm)

P_{net} is the net input power to the transmitting antenna (W)

g is gain of the transmitting antenna (dBi)

d is distance from the transmitting antenna to the receiving point (m)

Figure 6. Example fully anechoic chamber measurement setup

6. Measurement Results

Measurement results are given in Table 3, Table 4 and Table 5.

Table 3. Measurement results of HF-0191

Frequency (MHz)	Nominal Field Strength (A/m)	Correction Factor (dB)	Measurement Uncertainty (k=2) (dB)
30	0,150	0,51	0,43
50	0,150	-0,72	
70	0,150	-0,54	
100	0,150	-0,26	
200	0,150	-0,26	
300	0,150	0,02	
400	0,150	-0,01	
500	0,050	-0,33	0,69
600	0,050	-0,12	
700	0,090	-0,31	
800	0,100	-0,46	
900	0,100	-0,49	
1000	0,100	-0,47	

Table 4. Measurement results of Narda EFA-300, BN 2245/90.31

Frequency (kHz)	Nominal Field Strength (V/m)	Correction Factor (dB)	Measurement Uncertainty (k=2) (dB)
0,01	50	-0,18	0,49
0,02		-0,26	
0,05	100	-0,09	0,37
0,05	1000	-0,09	
0,05	2000	0,00	
0,1	50	-0,35	0,49
0,4		-0,35	
1		-0,35	
5		-0,26	
7		-0,26	
10		-0,18	
15		-0,09	
20		0,09	
23		0,30	
25		0,51	
27		0,91	
30		2,01	

Table 5. Measurement results of HI-6053

Frequency (GHz)	Nominal Field Strength (V/m)	Correction Factor (dB)	Measurement Uncertainty (k=2) (dB)
0,01	20	-	-
0,03		-0,45	0,62
0,05		-1,09	
0,07		-1,16	
0,1		-1,12	
0,2		-0,65	
0,3		-0,54	
0,5		-1,02	0,69
0,7		-0,47	
0,9		0,14	
1		-	-
1,5		-	
2		0,50	0,51
2,45		0,26	
3		1,14	
4		0,16	
5		0,43	
6		0,19	
7		-0,23	
8		-0,33	
9		0,04	
13		-0,87	
18		-2,26	

Table 5. Measurement results of HI-6053 (Continued)

Frequency (GHz)	Nominal Field Strength (V/m)	Correction Factor (dB)	Measurement Uncertainty (k=2) (dB)
20	20	-	-
25		-	-
27		-2,68	0,51
30		-1,28	
35		0,25	
40		2,23	

7. Detailed Uncertainty Budgets

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of 30 MHz - 400 MHz for HF-0191 measurements						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard uncertainty contribution (dB)
Accuracy of the power meter with power sensor	B	0,047	Normal	2	0,5	0,012
Attenuator accuracy	B	0,300	Normal	2	0,5	0,075
Placement of the probe	B	0,092	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,053
Field homogeneity	B	0,247	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,143
TEM cell impedance	B	0,365	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,5	0,105
TEM cell output mismatch	B	0,046	U-distribution	$\sqrt{2}$	0,5	0,016
Repeatability	A	0,078	Normal	1	1	0,078
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0,43

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of 500 MHz - 1000 MHz for HF-0191 measurements						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard uncertainty contribution (dB)
Power sensor accuracy	B	0,019	Normal	2	0,5	0,005
Power meter accuracy	B	0,068	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,5	0,020
Directional coupler accuracy	B	0,070	Normal	2	0,5	0,018
Antenna gain accuracy	B	0,580	Normal	2	0,5	0,145
Antenna / probe alignment	B	0,092	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,053
Antenna / probe distance	B	0,181	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,105
Reflections in chamber	B	0,412	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,238
Effective sensor position	B	0,092	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,053
Reflections probe / holder	B	0,086	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,050
Reflections antenna / probe	B	0,043	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,025
Temperature effects	B	0,189	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,5	0,055
Forward power sensor / directional coupler mismatch	B	0,177	U-Shape	$\sqrt{2}$	0,5	0,063
Reverse power sensor / directional coupler mismatch	B	0,183	U-Shape	$\sqrt{2}$	0,5	0,065
Antenna / directional coupler mismatch	B	0,124	U-Shape	$\sqrt{2}$	0,5	0,044
Repeatability	A	0,084	Normal	1	1	0,084
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0,69

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of 0,01 kHz - 30 kHz for EFA-300, BN 2245/90.31 measurements (Except 0,05 kHz frequency)						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard uncertainty contribution (dB)
Accuracy of the power meter with power sensor	B	0,009	Normal	2	0,5	0,002
Attenuator accuracy	B	0,300	Normal	2	0,5	0,075
Placement of the probe	B	0,090	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,052
Field homogeneity	B	0,347	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,200
TEM cell impedance	B	0,289	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,5	0,083
TEM cell output mismatch	B	0,033	U-distribution	$\sqrt{2}$	0,5	0,012
Repeatability	A	0,059	Normal	1	1	0,059
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0,49

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency 0,05 kHz for EFA-300, BN 2245/90.31 measurements						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard uncertainty contribution (dB)
Accuracy of the high voltage probe with multimeter	B	0,240	Normal	2	1	0,120
Placement of the probe	B	0,088	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,051
Field homogeneity	B	0,175	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,101
Fringing field effects	B	0,089	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,051
Repeatability	A	0,062	Normal	1	1	0,062
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0,37

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of 30 MHz - 300 MHz for HI-6053 measurements						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard uncertainty contribution (dB)
Accuracy of the power meter with power sensor	B	0,039	Normal	2	0,5	0,010
Attenuator accuracy	B	0,300	Normal	2	0,5	0,075
Placement of the probe	B	0,186	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,107
Field homogeneity	B	0,361	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,208
TEM cell impedance	B	0,328	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,5	0,095
TEM cell output mismatch	B	0,046	U-distribution	$\sqrt{2}$	0,5	0,016
Repeatability	A	0,159	Normal	1	1	0,159
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0,62

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of 500 MHz - 900 MHz for HI-6053 measurements						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard uncertainty contribution (dB)
Power sensor accuracy	B	0,019	Normal	2	0,5	0,005
Power meter accuracy	B	0,068	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,5	0,020
Directional coupler accuracy	B	0,070	Normal	2	0,5	0,018
Antenna gain accuracy	B	0,580	Normal	2	0,5	0,145
Antenna / probe alignment	B	0,207	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,120
Antenna / probe distance	B	0,186	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,107
Reflections in chamber	B	0,233	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,135
Effective sensor position	B	0,148	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,085
Reflections probe / holder	B	0,086	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,050
Reflections antenna / probe	B	0,043	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,025
Temperature effects	B	0,189	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,5	0,055
Forward power sensor / directional coupler mismatch	B	0,177	U-Shape	$\sqrt{2}$	0,5	0,063
Reverse power sensor / directional coupler mismatch	B	0,183	U-Shape	$\sqrt{2}$	0,5	0,065
Antenna / directional coupler mismatch	B	0,124	U-Shape	$\sqrt{2}$	0,5	0,044
Repeatability	A	0,175	Normal	1	1	0,175
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0,69

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of 2 GHz - 40 GHz for HI-6053 measurements						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard uncertainty contribution (dB)
Power sensor accuracy	B	0,223	Normal	2	0,5	0,056
Power meter accuracy	B	0,068	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,5	0,020
Directional coupler accuracy	B	0,190	Normal	2	0,5	0,048
Antenna gain accuracy	B	0,580	Normal	2	0,5	0,145
Antenna / probe alignment	B	0,097	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,056
Antenna / probe distance	B	0,079	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,046
Reflections in chamber	B	0,050	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,029
Effective sensor position	B	0,148	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,085
Reflections probe / holder	B	0,086	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,050
Reflections antenna / probe	B	0,043	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0,025
Temperature effects	B	0,189	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,5	0,055
Forward power sensor / directional coupler mismatch	B	0,177	U-Shape	$\sqrt{2}$	0,5	0,063
Reverse power sensor / directional coupler mismatch	B	0,183	U-Shape	$\sqrt{2}$	0,5	0,065
Antenna / directional coupler mismatch	B	0,124	U-Shape	$\sqrt{2}$	0,5	0,044
Repeatability	A	0,095	Normal	1	1	0,095
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0,51

MEASUREMENT REPORT

Supplementary Comparison on Electric / Magnetic Field Strength and Magnetic Flux Density Measurements

Development of RF and Microwave Metrology Capability II

22RPT04 RFMicrowave2

1. Participant Information

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2. Measurement Date

Measurement Dates	September 3 rd – 11 th , 2025
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3. Environmental Condition

Temperature (°C)	23.0 ± 2.0
Relative Humidity (%rh)	55 ± 15

4. Traveling Standards Specification

No.	Name	Manufacturer/Model	Serial number	Frequency range
1	Magnetic field probe	Narda ELT Probe 100 cm ²	M-1859	10 Hz – 400 kHz
	Field meter	Narda ELT-400	O-0450	
2	Magnetic field probe	Narda HF-0191	A-0310	27 MHz – 1 GHz
	Field meter	Narda NBM-550	B-1002	
3	Electric field probe	Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300	A-0074	5 Hz – 32 kHz
	Field meter	Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300	A-0098	
4	Electric field probe	ETS-Lindgren HI-6053	00224858	10 MHz – 40 GHz

5. References Used in Measurement

The measurements are metrologically traceable to national/international standards.

Name of Equipment	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No
Helmholtz coil	CMI	Ø 40 cm, single turn, unshielded	01
Parallel plate capacitor	CMI	d = 50 cm	02
Crawford type TEM cell	CMI	septum high 25 cm	01
Tapered TEM cell	CMI	d = 211 mm (in reference position)	01
Horn antenna	Milan Chyba Eng.	R48, MC90VO22103E	002
Horn antenna	Milan Chyba Eng.	R100, R100-A2	002
Horn antenna	Milan Chyba Eng.	R140, R140-A2	002
Horn antenna	Milan Chyba Eng.	R220, MC42T61103-18	002

Horn antenna	Milan Chyba Eng.	R320, MC28TA611110-B	002
Power splitter	Hewlett-Packard	11667A	19396
Directional coupler	Hewlett-Packard	11691D	1212A02732
Directional coupler	Milan Chyba Eng.	R220, MC42SO35020	001
Directional coupler	ČVUT – Praha	R320	054
Multifunction calibrator	Wavetek	4800	29960
Transconductance amplifier	Datron	4600	27131
Power meter	Rohde & Schwarz	NRVD	835843/022
Power meter	Rohde & Schwarz	NRP2	104770
Power meter	Hewlett-Packard	436A	2410A19598
Power meter	Agilent	N1911A	MY45100570
Power sensor	Rohde & Schwarz	NRP-Z91	103222
Power sensor	Rohde & Schwarz	NRV-Z51	836400/024
Power sensor	Rohde & Schwarz	NRV-Z55	100290
Power sensor	Hewlett-Packard	R8486A	3318A03345
Signal generator	Keysight	33600A	MY53801294
RF synthesizer	Agilent	E4438C	US41461550
RF synthesizer	Hewlett-Packard	83630B	3722A00516
RF synthesizer	Agilent	E8257D	US46461139
Power amplifier	BONN Elektronik	BLWA 0210-25	974436-02
Power amplifier	BONN Elektronik	BLMA 2018-7.5	2113715
Power amplifier	MILMEGA	AS0102-8M	1007301
Power amplifier	RF Lambda	RAMP18G40GA2	21102700015
Steel scale	Preisser	500 mm	reg. no. 67
Measuring tape	Stabila	30 m	reg. no. 68

6. Measurement Procedures

The reference position of the probes and the settings of the field meters were always carried out in accordance with the Technical Protocol (prepared by Marko Berginc, SIQ, July 7th, 2025).

The calibration factor given in the tables is defined as follows:

$$CF = 20 \cdot \log\left(\frac{V_{REF}}{V_{DUT}}\right)$$

where:

V_{REF} ... reference value of field quantity

V_{DUT} ... total field quantity value indicated by the Device Under Test

a. Low Frequency H-Field

The calibration of Narda ELT-400 was performed using an unshielded single turn Helmholtz coil (H. C.) with a diameter of 0.4 m. For frequencies 10 kHz and lower, the input current was

generated using a multifunction calibrator and a transconductance amplifier. For frequencies 50 kHz and higher, the input current was measured using a coaxial shunt and a power sensor.

b. Low Frequency E-Field

The calibration of W&G EFA 300 was performed using a parallel plate capacitor (distance between electrodes 0.5 m). The input voltage was generated using a multifunction calibrator.

c. High Frequency H-Field

The calibration of Narda HF-0191 for frequencies 200 MHz and lower was performed using a Crawford TEM cell with a septum height of 0.25 m. For frequencies 300 MHz and higher, the calibration was carried out using a Tapered TEM cell. The power delivered to the TEM cells was monitored using a power sensor.

d. High Frequency E-Field

The calibration of ETS Lindgren HI-6053 was performed using:

- A Crawford TEM cell with a septum height of 0.25 m for frequencies up to 200 MHz
- A Tapered TEM cell for frequencies 300 MHz – 3000 MHz
- Standard horn antennas (an octave-band) for frequencies 4 GHz – 40 GHz in a fully anechoic chamber. The distance between the probe and the antenna aperture was 1 m.

The power delivered to the TEM cells / standard horn antennas was monitored using a power sensor.

7. Measurement Results

a. Narda ELT Probe 100 cm², s/n: M-1859

B_{REF} (μT)	Frequency (kHz)	CF (dB)	U_c (k = 2) (dB)
10	0.03	0.31	0.23
10	0.055	0.21	0.23
10	0.1	0.18	0.23
10	1	0.16	0.23
10	3	0.18	0.23
10	5	0.18	0.23
10	10	0.19	0.23
3	50	0.13	0.31
3	100	0.11	0.31
3	200	0.07	0.40
3	300	0.23	0.40
3	400	2.85	0.43

b. Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300, s/n: A-0074

E_{REF} (V/m)	Frequency (kHz)	CF (dB)	$U_C (k = 2)$ (dB)
50	0.01	0.09	0.23
50	0.02	-0.04	0.23
500	0.02	0.04	0.17
100	0.05	0.01	0.18
1000	0.05	0.04	0.17
2000	0.05	0.04	0.17
50	0.1	-0.06	0.23
50	0.4	-0.07	0.22
50	1	-0.06	0.22
1000	1	0.01	0.17
50	5	-0.05	0.22
50	7	-0.02	0.22
50	10	0.03	0.22
1000	10	-0.05	0.16
50	15	0.16	0.22
50	20	0.35	0.23
50	23	0.55	0.23
50	25	0.77	0.24
50	27	1.16	0.25
50	30	2.24	0.30
500	30	2.24	0.16

c. Narda HF-0191, s/n: A-0310

H_{REF} (A/m)	Frequency (MHz)	CF (dB)	$U_C (k = 2)$ (dB)
0.150	30	0.84	0.47
0.150	50	-0.53	0.47
0.150	70	-0.41	0.47
0.150	100	-0.20	0.47
0.150	200	0.18	0.47
0.150	300	0.52	1.0
0.150	400	0.24	0.89
0.050	500	0.25	0.98
0.050	600	-0.13	0.90
0.100	700	-0.38	0.88
0.100	800	0.22	0.93
0.100	900	-0.95	0.93
0.100	1000	-0.07	0.95

d. ETS-Lindgren HI-6053, s/n: 00224858

E_{REF} (V/m)	Frequency (MHz)	CF (dB)	$U_c (k = 2)$ (dB)
20	10	3.47	0.48
20	30	-0.22	0.48
20	50	-0.87	0.48
20	70	-0.99	0.48
20	100	-0.92	0.48
20	200	-0.68	0.48
20	300	-0.44	0.94
20	500	-0.05	0.96
20	700	-0.09	0.98
20	900	0.38	0.97
20	1000	0.33	0.96
20	1500	0.21	0.95
20	2000	0.52	0.96
20	2450	0.37	0.98
20	3000	0.26	1.0
20	4000	0.48	0.83
20	5000	0.54	0.82
20	6000	1.07	0.82
20	7000	0.60	1.0
20	8000	0.29	0.87
20	9000	0.37	0.85
20	13000	-1.28	0.90
20	18000	-1.62	0.89
20	20000	-2.50	0.92
20	25000	-2.79	0.95
20	27000	-2.56	0.85
20	30000	-1.38	0.84
20	35000	0.40	0.93
20	40000	1.64	1.1

8. Detailed Uncertainty Budget

a. Narda ELT Probe 100 cm², s/n: M-1859

f = 30 Hz, B = 10 μ T

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.004	normal	1	1	0.004
tolerance of radius H. C.	B	0.069	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
distance tolerance of H. C.	B	0.104	rectangular	1.73	1	0.060
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field homogeneity	B	0.129	rectangular	1.73	1	0.075
current measurement	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
field meter noise	B	0.027	normal	1	1	0.027
Combined Uncertainty						0.117
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.23

f = 55 Hz, B = 10 μ T

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.004	normal	1	1	0.004
tolerance of radius H. C.	B	0.069	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
distance tolerance of H. C.	B	0.104	rectangular	1.73	1	0.060
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field homogeneity	B	0.129	rectangular	1.73	1	0.075
current measurement	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
field meter noise	B	0.027	normal	1	1	0.027
Combined Uncertainty						0.117
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.23

f = 100 Hz, B = 10 μ T

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.004	normal	1	1	0.004
tolerance of radius H. C.	B	0.069	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
distance tolerance of H. C.	B	0.104	rectangular	1.73	1	0.060
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field homogeneity	B	0.129	rectangular	1.73	1	0.075
current measurement	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
field meter noise	B	0.027	normal	1	1	0.027
Combined Uncertainty						0.117
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.23

f = 1 kHz, B = 10 μ T

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.004	normal	1	1	0.004
tolerance of radius H. C.	B	0.069	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
distance tolerance of H. C.	B	0.104	rectangular	1.73	1	0.060
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field homogeneity	B	0.129	rectangular	1.73	1	0.075
current measurement	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
field meter noise	B	0.027	normal	1	1	0.027
Combined Uncertainty						0.117
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.23

f = 3 kHz, B = 10 μ T

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.003	normal	1	1	0.003
tolerance of radius H. C.	B	0.069	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
distance tolerance of H. C.	B	0.104	rectangular	1.73	1	0.060
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field homogeneity	B	0.129	rectangular	1.73	1	0.075
current measurement	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
field meter noise	B	0.027	normal	1	1	0.027
Combined Uncertainty						0.117
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.23

f = 5 kHz, B = 10 μ T

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.003	normal	1	1	0.003
tolerance of radius H. C.	B	0.069	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
distance tolerance of H. C.	B	0.104	rectangular	1.73	1	0.060
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field homogeneity	B	0.129	rectangular	1.73	1	0.075
current measurement	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
field meter noise	B	0.027	normal	1	1	0.027
Combined Uncertainty						0.117
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.23

f = 10 kHz, B = 10 μ T

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.001	normal	1	1	0.001
tolerance of radius H. C.	B	0.069	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
distance tolerance of H. C.	B	0.104	rectangular	1.73	1	0.060
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field homogeneity	B	0.129	rectangular	1.73	1	0.075
current measurement	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
field meter noise	B	0.027	normal	1	1	0.027
Combined Uncertainty						0.117
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.23

f = 50 kHz, B = 3 μ T

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.002	normal	1	1	0.002
tolerance of radius H. C.	B	0.069	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
distance tolerance of H. C.	B	0.104	rectangular	1.73	1	0.060
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field homogeneity	B	0.129	rectangular	1.73	1	0.075
power sensor	B	0.022	normal	1	1	0.022
coaxial shunt	B	0.069	normal	1	1	0.069
field meter noise	B	0.088	normal	1	1	0.088
Combined Uncertainty						0.155
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.31

f = 100 kHz, B = 3 μ T

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.001	normal	1	1	0.001
tolerance of radius H. C.	B	0.069	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
distance tolerance of H. C.	B	0.104	rectangular	1.73	1	0.060
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field homogeneity	B	0.129	rectangular	1.73	1	0.075
power sensor	B	0.022	normal	1	1	0.022
coaxial shunt	B	0.069	normal	1	1	0.069
field meter noise	B	0.088	normal	1	1	0.088
Combined Uncertainty						0.155
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.31

f = 200 kHz, B = 3 μ T

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.002	normal	1	1	0.002
tolerance of radius H. C.	B	0.069	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
distance tolerance of H. C.	B	0.104	rectangular	1.73	1	0.060
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field homogeneity	B	0.257	rectangular	1.73	1	0.148
power sensor	B	0.022	normal	1	1	0.022
coaxial shunt	B	0.069	normal	1	1	0.069
field meter noise	B	0.087	normal	1	1	0.087
Combined Uncertainty						0.201
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.40

f = 300 kHz, B = 3 μ T

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.003	normal	1	1	0.003
tolerance of radius H. C.	B	0.069	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
distance tolerance of H. C.	B	0.104	rectangular	1.73	1	0.060
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field homogeneity	B	0.257	rectangular	1.73	1	0.148
power sensor	B	0.022	normal	1	1	0.022
coaxial shunt	B	0.069	normal	1	1	0.069
field meter noise	B	0.089	normal	1	1	0.089
Combined Uncertainty						0.202
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.40

f = 400 kHz, B = 3 μ T

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.001	normal	1	1	0.001
tolerance of radius H. C.	B	0.069	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
distance tolerance of H. C.	B	0.104	rectangular	1.73	1	0.060
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field homogeneity	B	0.257	rectangular	1.73	1	0.148
power sensor	B	0.022	normal	1	1	0.022
coaxial shunt	B	0.069	normal	1	1	0.069
field meter noise	B	0.120	normal	1	1	0.120
Combined Uncertainty						0.217
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.43

b. Wandel & Goltermann EFA-300, s/n: A-0074

f = 10 Hz, E = 50 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.027	normal	1	1	0.027
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.076	normal	1	1	0.076
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.114
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.23

f = 20 Hz, E = 50 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.031	normal	1	1	0.031
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.073	normal	1	1	0.073
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.114
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.23

f = 20 Hz, E = 500 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.027	normal	1	1	0.027
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.001	normal	1	1	0.001
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.086
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.17

f = 50 Hz, E = 100 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.038	normal	1	1	0.038
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.018	normal	1	1	0.018
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.091
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.18

f = 50 Hz, E = 1000 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.027	normal	1	1	0.027
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.000	normal	1	1	0.000
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.086
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.17

f = 50 Hz, E = 2000 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.027	normal	1	1	0.027
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.000	normal	1	1	0.000
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.086
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.17

f = 100 Hz, E = 50 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.028	normal	1	1	0.028
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.073	normal	1	1	0.073
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.113
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.23

f = 400 Hz, E = 50 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.025	normal	1	1	0.025
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.073	normal	1	1	0.073
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.112
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.22

f = 1 kHz, E = 50 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.020	normal	1	1	0.020
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.073	normal	1	1	0.073
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.111
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.22

f = 1 kHz, E = 1000 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.020	normal	1	1	0.020
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.000	normal	1	1	0.000
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.084
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.17

f = 5 kHz, E = 50 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.004	normal	1	1	0.004
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.073	normal	1	1	0.073
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.109
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.22

f = 7 kHz, E = 50 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.003	normal	1	1	0.003
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.074	normal	1	1	0.074
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.110
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.22

f = 10 kHz, E = 50 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.004	normal	1	1	0.004
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.075	normal	1	1	0.075
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.110
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.22

f = 10 kHz, E = 1000 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.007	normal	1	1	0.007
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.000	normal	1	1	0.000
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.082
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.16

f = 15 kHz, E = 50 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.004	normal	1	1	0.004
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.077	normal	1	1	0.077
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.112
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.22

f = 20 kHz, E = 50 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.004	normal	1	1	0.004
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.080	normal	1	1	0.080
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.114
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.23

f = 23 kHz, E = 50 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.004	normal	1	1	0.004
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.084	normal	1	1	0.084
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.117
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.23

f = 25 kHz, E = 50 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.005	normal	1	1	0.005
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.089	normal	1	1	0.089
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.120
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.24

f = 27 kHz, E = 50 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.006	normal	1	1	0.006
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.097	normal	1	1	0.097
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.127
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.25

f = 30 kHz, E = 50 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.007	normal	1	1	0.007
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.125	normal	1	1	0.125
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.149
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.30

f = 30 kHz, E = 500 V/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.007	normal	1	1	0.007
reference voltage accuracy	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
distance between plates	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
field meter noise	B	0.001	normal	1	1	0.001
field distortion	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Combined Uncertainty						0.082
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.16

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f = 30 MHz, H = 0.15 A/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.017	normal	1	1	0.017
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.180	rectangular	1.73	1	0.104
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.115	rectangular	1.73	1	0.066
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.065	normal	1	1	0.065
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.086	U-shape	1.41	1	0.061
Combined Uncertainty						0.237
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.47

f = 50 MHz, H = 0.15 A/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.008	normal	1	1	0.008
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.180	rectangular	1.73	1	0.104
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.115	rectangular	1.73	1	0.066
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.065	normal	1	1	0.065
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.086	U-shape	1.41	1	0.061
Combined Uncertainty						0.237
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.47

f = 70 MHz, H = 0.15 A/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.006	normal	1	1	0.006
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.180	rectangular	1.73	1	0.104
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.115	rectangular	1.73	1	0.066
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.065	normal	1	1	0.065
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.086	U-shape	1.41	1	0.061
Combined Uncertainty						0.237
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.47

f = 100 MHz, H = 0.15 A/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.008	normal	1	1	0.008
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.180	rectangular	1.73	1	0.104
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.115	rectangular	1.73	1	0.066
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.065	normal	1	1	0.065
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.086	U-shape	1.41	1	0.061
Combined Uncertainty						0.237
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.47

f = 200 MHz, H = 0.15 A/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.005	normal	1	1	0.005
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.180	rectangular	1.73	1	0.104
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.115	rectangular	1.73	1	0.066
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.065	normal	1	1	0.065
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.086	U-shape	1.41	1	0.061
Combined Uncertainty						0.237
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.47

f = 300 MHz, H = 0.15 A/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.009	normal	1	1	0.009
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.150	rectangular	1.73	1	0.087
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.100	rectangular	1.73	1	0.058
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.214	rectangular	1.73	1	0.124
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.628	U-shape	1.41	1	0.444
Combined Uncertainty						0.515
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						1.0

f = 400 MHz, H = 0.15 A/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.008	normal	1	1	0.008
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.150	rectangular	1.73	1	0.087
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.100	rectangular	1.73	1	0.058
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.214	rectangular	1.73	1	0.124
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.509	U-shape	1.41	1	0.360
Combined Uncertainty						0.445
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.89

f = 500 MHz, H = 0.05 A/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.070	normal	1	1	0.070
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.150	rectangular	1.73	1	0.087
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.100	rectangular	1.73	1	0.058
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.214	rectangular	1.73	1	0.124
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.582	U-shape	1.41	1	0.411
Combined Uncertainty						0.492
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.98

f = 600 MHz, H = 0.05 A/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.078	normal	1	1	0.078
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.150	rectangular	1.73	1	0.087
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.100	rectangular	1.73	1	0.058
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.214	rectangular	1.73	1	0.124
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.503	U-shape	1.41	1	0.356
Combined Uncertainty						0.448
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.90

f = 700 MHz, H = 0.1 A/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.024	normal	1	1	0.024
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.150	rectangular	1.73	1	0.087
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.100	rectangular	1.73	1	0.058
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.214	rectangular	1.73	1	0.124
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.500	U-shape	1.41	1	0.353
Combined Uncertainty						0.440
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.88

f = 800 MHz, H = 0.1 A/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.016	normal	1	1	0.016
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.150	rectangular	1.73	1	0.087
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.100	rectangular	1.73	1	0.058
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.214	rectangular	1.73	1	0.124
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.541	U-shape	1.41	1	0.383
Combined Uncertainty						0.464
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.93

f = 900 MHz, H = 0.1 A/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.015	normal	1	1	0.015
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.150	rectangular	1.73	1	0.087
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.100	rectangular	1.73	1	0.058
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.214	rectangular	1.73	1	0.124
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.541	U-shape	1.41	1	0.382
Combined Uncertainty						0.463
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.93

f = 1000 MHz, H = 0.1 A/m

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.016	normal	1	1	0.016
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.150	rectangular	1.73	1	0.087
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.100	rectangular	1.73	1	0.058
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.214	rectangular	1.73	1	0.124
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.564	U-shape	1.41	1	0.399
Combined Uncertainty						0.477
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.95

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f = 10 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.037	normal	1	1	0.037
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.180	rectangular	1.73	1	0.104
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.115	rectangular	1.73	1	0.066
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.065	normal	1	1	0.065
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.086	U-shape	1.41	1	0.061
Combined Uncertainty						0.240
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.48

f = 30 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.024	normal	1	1	0.024
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.180	rectangular	1.73	1	0.104
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.115	rectangular	1.73	1	0.066
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.065	normal	1	1	0.065
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.086	U-shape	1.41	1	0.061
Combined Uncertainty						0.238
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.48

f = 50 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.023	normal	1	1	0.023
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.180	rectangular	1.73	1	0.104
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.115	rectangular	1.73	1	0.066
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.065	normal	1	1	0.065
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.086	U-shape	1.41	1	0.061
Combined Uncertainty						0.238
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.48

f = 70 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.022	normal	1	1	0.022
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.180	rectangular	1.73	1	0.104
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.115	rectangular	1.73	1	0.066
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.065	normal	1	1	0.065
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.086	U-shape	1.41	1	0.061
Combined Uncertainty						0.238
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.48

f = 100 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.023	normal	1	1	0.023
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.180	rectangular	1.73	1	0.104
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.115	rectangular	1.73	1	0.066
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.065	normal	1	1	0.065
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.086	U-shape	1.41	1	0.061
Combined Uncertainty						0.238
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.48

f = 200 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.023	normal	1	1	0.023
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.180	rectangular	1.73	1	0.104
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.115	rectangular	1.73	1	0.066
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.086	rectangular	1.73	1	0.050
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.065	normal	1	1	0.065
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.086	U-shape	1.41	1	0.061
Combined Uncertainty						0.238
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.48

f = 300 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.024	normal	1	1	0.024
tapered TEM cell calibration	B	0.400	normal	1	1	0.400
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.070	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.060	rectangular	1.73	1	0.035
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.097	U-shape	1.41	1	0.069
Combined Uncertainty						0.469
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.94

f = 500 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.025	normal	1	1	0.025
tapered TEM cell calibration	B	0.400	normal	1	1	0.400
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.070	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.060	rectangular	1.73	1	0.035
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.162	U-shape	1.41	1	0.114
Combined Uncertainty						0.478
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.96

f = 700 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.025	normal	1	1	0.025
tapered TEM cell calibration	B	0.400	normal	1	1	0.400
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.070	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.060	rectangular	1.73	1	0.035
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.225	U-shape	1.41	1	0.159
Combined Uncertainty						0.490
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.98

f = 900 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.026	normal	1	1	0.026
tapered TEM cell calibration	B	0.400	normal	1	1	0.400
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.070	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.060	rectangular	1.73	1	0.035
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.211	U-shape	1.41	1	0.149
Combined Uncertainty						0.487
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.97

f = 1000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.026	normal	1	1	0.026
tapered TEM cell calibration	B	0.400	normal	1	1	0.400
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.070	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.060	rectangular	1.73	1	0.035
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.176	U-shape	1.41	1	0.124
Combined Uncertainty						0.480
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.96

f = 1500 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.026	normal	1	1	0.026
tapered TEM cell calibration	B	0.400	normal	1	1	0.400
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.070	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.060	rectangular	1.73	1	0.035
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.132	U-shape	1.41	1	0.094
Combined Uncertainty						0.473
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.95

f = 2000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.049	normal	1	1	0.049
tapered TEM cell calibration	B	0.400	normal	1	1	0.400
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.070	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.060	rectangular	1.73	1	0.035
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.176	U-shape	1.41	1	0.124
Combined Uncertainty						0.482
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.96

f = 2450 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.064	normal	1	1	0.064
tapered TEM cell calibration	B	0.400	normal	1	1	0.400
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.070	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.060	rectangular	1.73	1	0.035
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.215	U-shape	1.41	1	0.152
Combined Uncertainty						0.492
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.98

f = 3000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.049	normal	1	1	0.049
tapered TEM cell calibration	B	0.400	normal	1	1	0.400
position dev. in the E dir.	B	0.070	rectangular	1.73	1	0.040
position dev. in the H dir.	B	0.060	rectangular	1.73	1	0.035
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
septum height	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
field distortion	B	0.300	rectangular	1.73	1	0.173
effect of standing waves	B	0.262	U-shape	1.41	1	0.186
Combined Uncertainty						0.501
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						1.0

f = 4000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.070	normal	1	1	0.070
antenna gain calibration	B	0.350	normal	1	1	0.350
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
distance measurement error	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
levelling error	B	0.058	normal	1	1	0.058
directional coupler	B	0.091	normal	1	1	0.091
effect of standing waves	B	0.150	U-shape	1.41	1	0.106
Combined Uncertainty						0.415
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.83

f = 5000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.030	normal	1	1	0.030
antenna gain calibration	B	0.350	normal	1	1	0.350
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
distance measurement error	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
levelling error	B	0.058	normal	1	1	0.058
directional coupler	B	0.091	normal	1	1	0.091
effect of standing waves	B	0.150	U-shape	1.41	1	0.106
Combined Uncertainty						0.410
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.82

f = 6000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.035	normal	1	1	0.035
antenna gain calibration	B	0.350	normal	1	1	0.350
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
distance measurement error	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
levelling error	B	0.058	normal	1	1	0.058
directional coupler	B	0.091	normal	1	1	0.091
effect of standing waves	B	0.150	U-shape	1.41	1	0.106
Combined Uncertainty						0.410
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.82

f = 7000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.123	normal	1	1	0.123
antenna gain calibration	B	0.350	normal	1	1	0.350
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
distance measurement error	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
levelling error	B	0.058	normal	1	1	0.058
directional coupler	B	0.300	normal	1	1	0.300
effect of standing waves	B	0.150	U-shape	1.41	1	0.106
Combined Uncertainty						0.514
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						1.0

f = 8000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.155	normal	1	1	0.155
antenna gain calibration	B	0.350	normal	1	1	0.350
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
distance measurement error	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
levelling error	B	0.058	normal	1	1	0.058
directional coupler	B	0.091	normal	1	1	0.091
effect of standing waves	B	0.150	U-shape	1.41	1	0.106
Combined Uncertainty						0.437
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.87

f = 9000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.111	normal	1	1	0.111
antenna gain calibration	B	0.350	normal	1	1	0.350
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
distance measurement error	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
levelling error	B	0.058	normal	1	1	0.058
directional coupler	B	0.091	normal	1	1	0.091
effect of standing waves	B	0.150	U-shape	1.41	1	0.106
Combined Uncertainty						0.424
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.85

f = 13000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.062	normal	1	1	0.062
antenna gain calibration	B	0.350	normal	1	1	0.350
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
distance measurement error	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
levelling error	B	0.058	normal	1	1	0.058
directional coupler	B	0.199	normal	1	1	0.199
effect of standing waves	B	0.150	U-shape	1.41	1	0.106
Combined Uncertainty						0.450
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.90

f = 18000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.035	normal	1	1	0.035
antenna gain calibration	B	0.350	normal	1	1	0.350
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
distance measurement error	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
levelling error	B	0.058	normal	1	1	0.058
directional coupler	B	0.199	normal	1	1	0.199
effect of standing waves	B	0.150	U-shape	1.41	1	0.106
Combined Uncertainty						0.447
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.89

f = 20000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.187	normal	1	1	0.187
antenna gain calibration	B	0.350	normal	1	1	0.350
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
distance measurement error	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
levelling error	B	0.058	normal	1	1	0.058
directional coupler	B	0.091	normal	1	1	0.091
effect of standing waves	B	0.207	U-shape	1.41	1	0.146
Combined Uncertainty						0.461
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.92

f = 25000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.246	normal	1	1	0.246
antenna gain calibration	B	0.350	normal	1	1	0.350
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
distance measurement error	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
levelling error	B	0.058	normal	1	1	0.058
directional coupler	B	0.091	normal	1	1	0.091
effect of standing waves	B	0.150	U-shape	1.41	1	0.106
Combined Uncertainty						0.477
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.95

f = 27000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.108	normal	1	1	0.108
antenna gain calibration	B	0.350	normal	1	1	0.350
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
distance measurement error	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
levelling error	B	0.058	normal	1	1	0.058
directional coupler	B	0.091	normal	1	1	0.091
effect of standing waves	B	0.150	U-shape	1.41	1	0.106
Combined Uncertainty						0.423
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.85

f = 30000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.087	normal	1	1	0.087
antenna gain calibration	B	0.350	normal	1	1	0.350
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
distance measurement error	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
levelling error	B	0.058	normal	1	1	0.058
directional coupler	B	0.091	normal	1	1	0.091
effect of standing waves	B	0.150	U-shape	1.41	1	0.106
Combined Uncertainty						0.418
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.84

f = 35000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.227	normal	1	1	0.227
antenna gain calibration	B	0.350	normal	1	1	0.350
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
distance measurement error	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
levelling error	B	0.058	normal	1	1	0.058
directional coupler	B	0.091	normal	1	1	0.091
effect of standing waves	B	0.150	U-shape	1.41	1	0.106
Combined Uncertainty						0.467
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						0.93

f = 40000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k factor	Sens. coeff.	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.362	normal	1	1	0.362
antenna gain calibration	B	0.350	normal	1	1	0.350
probe angle deviation	B	0.033	rectangular	1.73	1	0.019
distance measurement error	B	0.172	rectangular	1.73	1	0.099
RF power meas. accuracy	B	0.107	normal	1	1	0.107
levelling error	B	0.058	normal	1	1	0.058
directional coupler	B	0.091	normal	1	1	0.091
effect of standing waves	B	0.150	U-shape	1.41	1	0.106
Combined Uncertainty						0.546
Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)						1.1

The standard uncertainty of measurement has been determined in accordance with JCGM 100:2008 document. The reported expanded uncertainty of measurement is stated as the standard uncertainty of measurement multiplied by the coverage factor k corresponding to a coverage probability of approximately 95 %, which for normal distribution corresponds to a coverage factor $k = 2$.

Supplementary comparison report on electric strength measurements

Development of RF and Microwave Metrology Capability II (22RPT04 RF&Microwave2)

ANNEX A_ Report of measuring results_IMBIH

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION

Laboratory Name:	Institute of Metrology of Bosnia and Herzegovina (IMBIH)
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OTHER DATA

- Location: Slovenian Institute of Quality and Metrology (SIQ)
- Temperature: (23 ± 2) °C
- Relative Humidity: (50 ± 20) %.
- Nominal value of the electrical field (50 V/m, 200 V/m, 100 V/m, 50 V/m, 500 V/m)
- Measurement date: 29.07.2025.

STANDARDS USED FOR MEASUREMENT

Instrument Name	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial Number	Traceability
Electric field probe	Narda	EFA-300 (5 Hz – 32 kHz)	BN 2245/90.31	UME
Calibrator +amplifier	Fluke	5720A	-	SIQ
Laser distance meter	-	-	-	SIQ

DESCRIPTION OF MEASUREMENT METHOD

Within the scope of the Project of Development of RF and Microwave Metrology Capability II (22RPT04 RFMicrowave2), activity A3.3.3, Institute of Metrology of Bosnia and Herzegovina (IMBIH) performed the intercomparison regarding strength of electric field measurements. Measurements were done at Slovenian Institute of Metrology and Quality (SIQ) in Ljubljana, Slovenia. For this kind of measurements, it was used parallel plate capacitor designed and built at IMBIH, electric field probe Narda EFA-300 (5 Hz – 32 kHz), Fluke 5720A calibrator with amplifier for generating AC voltage and laptop for collecting measuring results. Distance between plates of the capacitor is $d = 0.705$ m and it was measured with laser distance meter. Measurement setup is shown on Figure 1.

Figure 1

DESCRIPTION OF TRACEABILITY

Traceability of the measurements for used standards has established through Institute of Metrology of Turkey (UME) and Slovenian Institute of Quality and Metrology (SIQ).

MEASUREMENT RESULTS

Narda EFA-300		
<i>f</i> (kHz)	Measured <i>CF</i> (<i>l</i>)	UNC of <i>CF</i> (CL = 95 %) (<i>l</i>)
0.01	0.97	0.004
0.02	0.96	0.003
0.02	0.68	0.002
0.05	0.96	0.004
0.1	0.95	0.003
0.4	0.96	0.003
1	0.96	0.004
5	0.97	0.004
10	0.98	0.004
15	1.00	0.004
20	1.02	0.004
25	1.07	0.004
30	1.27	0.006
30	1.28	0.006

UNCERTAINTY BUDGET EXAMPLE FOR EACH FIELD REALIZATION

Model function: $E_M + \delta C + \delta D + \delta P_{calibration} + \delta P_{reslution} + \delta H = E_{calc}$

E_M - Measured electric field using E-field probe;

E_{calc} - Calculated electric field;

δC - Uncertainty due to the calibrator 5720A used for generating voltage between parallel plates of the capacitor;

δD - Uncertainty due to distance between plates of capacitor;

δP_{cal} – Uncertainty due to E-field probe under calibration;

δP_{res} – Uncertainty due to the resolution of the E-field probe;

δH – Uncertainty due to the inhomogeneity of the E- field.

Uncertainty budget 50 V/m @ the frequency 0,01 kHz for EFA-300, BN 2245/90.31 measurements						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (V/m)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard uncertainty contribution (V/m)
Uncertainty of the calibrator	B	0.0135	Rectangular	$2\sqrt{3}$	1	0.0039
Uncertainty due to distance	A	0.18	Normal	2	1	0.09
Uncertainty due to E-field probe under calibration	A	0.06	Normal	2	1	0.03
Uncertainty due to the resolution of the E-field probe	B	0.03	Rectangular	$2\sqrt{3}$	1	0.01
Uncertainty due to the inhomogeneity of the E-field	B	0.08	Normal	2	1	0.04
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0.21

Uncertainty budget 50 V/m @ the frequency 5 kHz for EFA-300, BN 2245/90.31 measurements						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (V/m)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard uncertainty contribution (V/m)
Uncertainty of the calibrator	B	0.0135	Rectangular	$2\sqrt{3}$	1	0.0039
Uncertainty due to distance	A	0.18	Normal	2	1	0.09
Uncertainty due to E-field probe under calibration	A	0.014	Normal	2	1	0.007
Uncertainty due to the resolution of the E-field probe	B	0.030	Rectangular	$2\sqrt{3}$	1	0.01
Uncertainty due to the inhomogeneity of the E-field	B	0.02	Normal	2	1	0.01
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0.19

Uncertainty budget 500 v/m @ the frequency 30 kHz for EFA-300, BN 2245/90.31 measurements						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (V/m)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard uncertainty contribution (V/m)
Uncertainty of the calibrator	B	0.135	Rectangular	$2\sqrt{3}$	1	0.039
Uncertainty due to distance	A	1.8	Normal	2	1	0.9
Uncertainty due to E-field probe under calibration	B	0.0	Normal	2	1	0.0
Uncertainty due to the resolution of the E-field probe	B	0.3	Rectangular	$2\sqrt{3}$	1	0.1
Uncertainty due to the inhomogeneity of the E-field	B	0.0	Normal	2	1	0.0
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						1.9

Acknowledgement

I would like to thank Slovenian Institute for Quality and Metrology (SIQ) for their great support to Institute of Metrology of Bosnia and Herzegovina (IMBIH) in realizing this kind of measurement campaign.

**Supplementary Comparison on Low-Frequency Electric and
Magnetic Field Measurements
(Slovenian External Loop)
RFMII-SC-E**

European Partnership 22RPT04 RFMicrowave2 – Activity A3.3.3 (external loop)

Report status: FINAL

Date: March 20, 2026

Pilot / reference laboratory: SIQ (Slovenian Institute of Quality and Metrology)

Coordinator: Left Right d.o.o. (evaluation support)

Participants: SIQ; LOVENO; Elektro Maribor; ZVD

European Partnership Co-funded by
the European Union

**METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP**

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1 Introduction

Within the scope of the Metrology Partnership project “Development of RF and Microwave Metrology Capability II” (22RPT04 RFMicrowave2), Activity A3.3.3 foresees the organisation of an intercomparison related to electric and magnetic field probe calibration.

The main comparison involves National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) and Designated Institutes and covers both low-frequency (LF) and high-frequency (HF) electric and magnetic field probes. The organisation and reporting principles follow the CCEM Guidelines for Planning, Organizing, Conducting and Reporting Key, Supplementary and Pilot Comparisons [1] and the structure prescribed in EURAMET Guide No. 4 [2].

In parallel with the main comparison, an additional external loop was organised in Slovenia in order to:

- involve external accredited laboratories that are not formal partners of the RFMicrowave2 project,
- strengthen national measurement capabilities in low-frequency electromagnetic field measurements,
- promote knowledge transfer between the national metrology institute and accredited testing laboratories,
- provide further technical impact of the RFMicrowave2 project at national level.

This report documents the results of this Slovenian external loop.

1.1 Measurand

The measurand of the comparison is the electric field strength E or magnetic flux density B realised in the SIQ metrology laboratory at specified frequencies and nominal field levels.

The electric field was generated in a parallel-plate field realisation system, while the magnetic field was generated in a Helmholtz coil system. For each frequency and nominal field level, SIQ established and characterised the reference field under controlled laboratory conditions.

The participating laboratories subsequently measured the same realised field using their own field probes and instrumentation under identical nominal conditions. The comparison therefore evaluates the degree of agreement between the field quantity measured by each participant and the reference field value established by SIQ.

Unlike the main comparison, where a comparison reference value (CRV) is determined as a weighted mean of participants’ results, the external loop was organised as a reference-based comparison. SIQ acted as the reference laboratory, and its measured field values constitute the reference values for each measurement point.

The compatibility of participants’ results with the SIQ reference values is evaluated using the normalised error E_n , calculated from the difference between the participant result and the reference value, taking into account the expanded uncertainties (coverage factor $k = 2$) associated with both quantities.

The external loop was coordinated by Left Right s.p., Ljubljana, Slovenia, which was responsible for the evaluation of the comparison results and the preparation of the present report.

The comparison was carried out in accordance with the principles described in the CCEM Guidelines and follows the reporting structure prescribed by EURAMET Guide No. 4 [2].

2 Comparison scheme

The Slovenian external loop was organised as a reference-based comparison with SIQ acting as the reference laboratory. The topology differs from the main RFMicrowave2 comparison,

which follows a ring circulation scheme and determines a comparison reference value (CRV) from participants' results.

In the external loop, the comparison was performed according to the following sequence:

1. SIQ established and characterised the reference field (electric or magnetic) at the specified frequency and nominal field level.
2. The reference field was realised in the SIQ metrology laboratory using a controlled field generation system (Helmholtz coil for magnetic field, parallel-plate system for electric field).
3. The participating laboratory performed measurements of the same realised field using its own probe and instrumentation under identical nominal conditions.
4. The participant's measured field value was compared to the SIQ reference value.

The comparison was therefore conducted without physical transfer of a travelling standard between laboratories. Instead, the realised field quantity itself constituted the comparison artefact. All measurements were performed at the SIQ premises under controlled environmental conditions.

For each measurement point, the SIQ result obtained immediately prior to the participant measurement was taken as the reference value. The evaluation of equivalence was performed by calculating the normalised error E_n between the participant result and the SIQ reference value, taking into account the expanded uncertainties (coverage factor $k = 2$) of both quantities.

This scheme ensures:

- traceability of the realised field to the SI through the SIQ measurement system,
- minimisation of transport-related stability effects,
- consistent environmental conditions for all participants,
- direct assessment of agreement with the national reference.

The comparison was limited to low-frequency electric and magnetic fields, in contrast to the main comparison which additionally includes high-frequency probes.

3 Participants

The Slovenian external loop involved the reference laboratory, a coordinating organisation, and three participating laboratories providing low-frequency electromagnetic field measurement services in Slovenia.

3.1 Coordinating organisation

Left Right s.p.

Ulica bratov Učakar 40

SI-1000 Ljubljana

Slovenia

Left Right s.p. acted as the coordinating organisation of the external loop and was responsible for:

- coordination of the comparison activities,
- evaluation and statistical analysis of the comparison results,
- preparation of the present report.

3.2 Reference laboratory

Slovenski Institut za Kakovost in Meroslovje (SIQ)

Mašera-Spasičeva 10
SI-1000 Ljubljana
Slovenia

SIQ acted as the reference laboratory and was responsible for:

- realisation and characterisation of the electric and magnetic reference fields,
- establishment of the reference values for each frequency and nominal field level,
- ensuring traceability of the realised field quantities to the SI.

All reference measurements were performed in the SIQ metrology laboratory under controlled environmental conditions.

3.3 Participating laboratories

Laboratorij OVENO - LOVENO

Hajdrihova 2
1000 Ljubljana
Slovenia

Elektro Maribor d.d.

Vetrinjska ulica 2
SI-2000 Maribor
Slovenia

ZVD Zavod za varstvo pri delu d.o.o.

Chengdujska cesta 25
SI-1260 Ljubljana-Polje
Slovenia

The participating laboratories are providers of low-frequency electric and magnetic field measurements and testing services. Their measurements were performed using their own field probes and instrumentation under the nominal field conditions realised by SIQ.

Each participant reported measured field values together with the associated expanded uncertainties (coverage factor $k = 2$), in accordance with the comparison protocol.

4 Transfer standard and field realisation systems

In contrast to conventional interlaboratory comparisons involving the circulation of a travelling standard, the Slovenian external loop was organised as a reference-based comparison without transfer of a physical artefact between laboratories.

The comparison artefact was the realised electromagnetic field quantity itself. For each measurement point, the electric or magnetic field was generated, stabilised, and characterised in the SIQ metrology laboratory, and subsequently measured by the participating laboratory under identical nominal conditions.

4.1 Magnetic field realisation

Low-frequency magnetic fields were realised using a Helmholtz coil system designed to generate a uniform magnetic flux density in a defined measurement volume. The coil geometry and driving

current were selected to ensure field homogeneity and stability at the specified frequencies and nominal flux density levels.

The magnetic flux density was established and characterised by SIQ using calibrated instrumentation traceable to the SI and corrected for main comparison deviation from mean value. The reference value at each frequency and nominal level was determined immediately prior to the participant measurement.

4.2 Electric field realisation

Low-frequency electric fields were realised using a parallel-plate field generation system providing a defined electric field strength between two electrodes. The electrode spacing, applied voltage, and system geometry ensured a well-defined and reproducible electric field in the measurement region.

The electric field strength was characterised by SIQ using calibrated instrumentation traceable to the SI and corrected for main comparison deviation from mean value. As for the magnetic field, the reference value for each measurement point was determined immediately prior to the participant measurement.

4.3 Stability and measurement sequence

All measurements were performed at the SIQ premises. For each frequency and nominal level, the following sequence was applied:

1. Realisation and stabilisation of the field quantity.
2. Determination of the SIQ reference value.
3. Measurement by the participating laboratory.

This approach minimised potential stability and transport effects and ensured that all participants measured the same realised field quantity under comparable environmental conditions.

Traceability of the comparison is therefore ensured through the SIQ measurement systems used to establish the electric and magnetic field quantities, that was corrected for deviation found in the main comparison cycle.

5 Measurement method and measurement points

Measurement method

The comparison was based on the measurement of realised low-frequency electric field strength E and magnetic flux density B established in the SIQ metrology laboratory.

For each measurement point, SIQ first stabilised and characterised the realised field quantity. The participating laboratory then positioned its probe within the defined measurement region and measured the field using its own instrumentation and measurement procedure.

Participants were instructed to:

- measure the realised field at the specified frequency and nominal level,
- apply their standard measurement procedure as used in routine calibration or testing,
- report the measured field value,
- report the associated expanded uncertainty (coverage factor $k = 2$).

No harmonisation of internal correction procedures was imposed; each laboratory applied its own calibration factors, correction methods, and uncertainty evaluation approach.

Measurement points

The comparison was limited to low-frequency quantities and included predefined frequency points and nominal field levels.

Magnetic field Magnetic flux density measurements were performed in the Helmholtz coil system at the specified frequency points and nominal magnetic flux density levels defined in the comparison protocol.

Electric field Electric field strength measurements were performed in the parallel-plate field generation system at the specified frequency points and nominal electric field strength levels defined in the comparison protocol.

For each measurement point, the nominal level served only as a setting parameter of the field generation system. The reference value used for evaluation was the field quantity determined by SIQ immediately prior to the participant measurement.

Reported quantities

Participants reported:

- measured electric field strength E or magnetic flux density B ,
- corresponding expanded uncertainty (coverage factor $k = 2$),
- relevant measurement conditions where applicable.

All reported measured values are expressed in linear units (V/m for electric field strength and μT for magnetic flux density). All uncertainties are reported either as absolute values or as relative to the measured values.

6 Measurement conditions and equipment

6.1 Environmental conditions

All measurements were performed at the SIQ metrology laboratory under controlled environmental conditions.

During the comparison measurements, the laboratory temperature and relative humidity were maintained within the normal operating ranges specified for the respective instrumentation and field generation systems. Environmental parameters were monitored throughout the measurement sessions.

No significant environmental deviations were observed that would influence the realised field quantities or the participant measurements beyond the reported uncertainty contributions.

6.2 Field generation systems

The magnetic field was generated using a Helmholtz coil system designed to provide a uniform magnetic flux density within a defined measurement volume. The coil system was driven by a stable low-frequency current source.

The electric field was generated using a parallel-plate field realisation system. The applied voltage and electrode spacing defined the electric field strength in the measurement region. The system geometry was designed to ensure reproducibility and field uniformity within the probe positioning area.

Both field generation systems are part of the SIQ metrology infrastructure and are maintained and calibrated within the SIQ quality system.

6.3 Reference measurement instrumentation

The reference field quantities were determined by SIQ using calibrated measurement instrumentation traceable to the SI. The instrumentation used for establishing the reference values is part of the SIQ metrology system and is regularly calibrated within the established traceability chain.

The reference value for each measurement point was determined immediately prior to the participant measurement in order to minimise potential drift effects.

Participant instrumentation

Each participating laboratory used its own field probe and associated measurement instrumentation. The instruments reported by the participants are summarised below.

Laboratorij OVENO - LOVENO LOVENO performed the measurements using:

a)

- Magnetic field probe:
Manufacturer: Narda Safety Test Solutions GmbH, model: 2245/90.10, serial number AV-0171
- Electric field probe:
Manufacturer: Narda Safety Test Solutions GmbH, model: 2245/90.31, serial number: J-0030
- Readout / measurement unit:
Instrument model: EFA-300 BN2245, serial number: M-0006

b)

- Electric & Magnetic field probe:
Manufacturer: Narda Safety Test Solutions GmbH, model: EHP50F, serial number 100WY70115
- Readout / measurement unit:
Instrument model: NBM-550 2401/01B, serial number: H-0134

The instrumentation was reported as calibrated and traceable to the SI through the laboratory's established calibration chain.

Elektro Maribor d.d. Elektro Maribor performed the measurements using:

- Magnetic field probe:
Manufacturer: MASCHEK, model: ESM-100, serial number: 972843
- Electric field probe:
Manufacturer: MASCHEK, model: ESM-100, serial number: 972843
- Readout / measurement unit:
Instrument model: 3D H/E Fieldmeter

The instrumentation was reported as calibrated and traceable to the SI through the laboratory's established calibration chain.

ZVD Zavod za varstvo pri delu d.o.o. ZVD performed the measurements using:

- Magnetic field probe:
Manufacturer: WAVECONTROL, model: WP400, serial number: 17WP100358
- Electric field probe:
Manufacturer: WAVECONTROL, model: WP400, serial number: 17WP100358
- Readout / measurement unit:
Instrument model: SMP2-Dual, serial number: 17SN0637

The instrumentation was reported as calibrated and traceable to the SI through the laboratory's established calibration chain.

7 Participants' results

The measurement results reported by the participating laboratories are summarised in Tables 1–4 for magnetic flux density and Tables 5–8 for electric field strength.

For each measurement point, the tables present:

- the frequency f and nominal field level B_n or E_n ,
- the reference value B_s or E_s established by SIQ,
- the expanded uncertainty of the reference value $U(B_s)$ or $U(E_s)$ ($k = 2$),
- the participant's measured field value B_x or E_x ,
- the participant's expanded uncertainty $U(B_x)$ or $U(E_x)$ ($k = 2$),
- the relative deviation from the reference value δB_x or δE_x ,
- the absolute value of the normalised error E_n .

All values are expressed in linear units. Relative quantities are expressed as dimensionless ratios.

7.1 Magnetic flux density

Tables 1–4 present the magnetic flux density results obtained in the Helmholtz coil system.

For each measurement point, the compatibility of the participant result with the SIQ reference value is evaluated using the normalised error $|E_n|$. Values of $|E_n| \leq 1$ indicate consistency within the stated expanded uncertainties.

Table 1: Magnetic flux density measurement results and Degree of Equivalence for Laboratory LOVENO (Probe EFA-300).

f (kHz)	B_n (μT)	B_s (μT)	$U(B_s)$ (μT)	B_x (μT)	$U(B_x)$ (μT)	δB_x	$ E_n $
0.03	10	9.80	0.17	9.69	0.87	-1.1 %	0.13
0.055	10	9.73	0.17	9.63	0.87	-1.0 %	0.11
0.1	10	9.69	0.17	9.60	0.86	-0.9 %	0.10
1	10	9.57	0.16	9.46	0.85	-1.1 %	0.12
3	10	9.54	0.16	9.51	0.86	-0.3 %	0.03
5	6	5.74	0.10	5.73	0.52	-0.1 %	0.01
10	3	2.85	0.05	2.84	0.26	-0.5 %	0.05

Table 2: Magnetic flux density measurement results and Degree of Equivalence for Laboratory LOVENO (Probe EHP50F).

f (kHz)	B_n (μT)	B_s (μT)	$U(B_s)$ (μT)	B_x (μT)	$U(B_x)$ (μT)	δB_x	$ E_n $
0.03	10	9.80	0.17	9.91	0.96	1.2 %	0.12
0.055	10	9.73	0.17	9.51	0.92	-2.3 %	0.24
0.1	10	9.69	0.17	9.50	0.92	-2.0 %	0.21
1	10	9.57	0.16	9.04	0.88	-5.5 %	0.59
3	10	9.54	0.16	9.16	0.63	-4.0 %	0.59
5	6	5.74	0.10	5.54	0.38	-3.5 %	0.50
10	3	2.85	0.05	2.75	0.19	-3.6 %	0.53

Table 3: Magnetic flux density measurement results and Degree of Equivalence for Elektro Maribor (Probe ESM-100).

f (kHz)	B_n (μT)	B_s (μT)	$U(B_s)$ (μT)	B_x (μT)	$U(B_x)$ (μT)	δB_x	$ E_n $
0.03	10	9.80	0.17	9.53	0.85	-2.7 %	0.31
0.055	10	9.73	0.17	9.54	0.85	-1.9 %	0.22
0.1	10	9.69	0.17	9.55	0.85	-1.5 %	0.17
1	10	9.57	0.16	9.54	0.85	-0.3 %	0.03
3	10	9.54	0.16	9.41	0.84	-1.4 %	0.15
5	6	5.74	0.10	5.66	0.51	-1.3 %	0.15
10	3	2.85	0.05	2.81	0.25	-1.6 %	0.18

Table 4: Magnetic flux density measurement results and Degree of Equivalence for ZVD (Probe WP400).

f (kHz)	B_n (μT)	B_s (μT)	$U(B_s)$ (μT)	B_x (μT)	$U(B_x)$ (μT)	δB_x	$ E_n $
0.03	10	9.80	0.17	9.41	0.85	-3.9 %	0.45
0.055	10	9.73	0.17	9.57	0.86	-1.6 %	0.18
0.1	10	9.69	0.17	9.24	0.83	-4.7 %	0.54
1	10	9.57	0.16	9.20	0.83	-3.9 %	0.44
3	10	9.54	0.16	9.31	0.84	-2.4 %	0.27
5	6	5.74	0.10	5.50	0.50	-4.1 %	0.46
10	3	2.85	0.05	2.81	0.25	-1.8 %	0.19

Figure 1: Relative deviations from the reference value (red line for nominal value, red area for uncertainty range) for magnetic fields from Tables 1 to 4.

7.2 Electric field strength

Tables 5–8 present the electric field strength results obtained in the parallel-plate field generation system.

The same evaluation procedure based on the normalised error E_n is applied.

Table 5: Electric field measurement results and Degree of Equivalence for Laboratory LOVENO (Probe EFA-300).

f (kHz)	E_n (V/m)	E_s (V/m)	$U(E_s)$ (V/m)	E_x (V/m)	$U(E_x)$ (V/m)	δE_x	$ E_n $
0.01	50	50.2	0.9	50.0	3.1	−0.5%	0.08
0.02	50	50.2	0.9	50.8	3.2	1.2%	0.18
0.02	500	507	7.2	506	31	−0.2%	0.03
0.05	100	100	1.5	101.1	6.3	0.8%	0.12
0.05	1000	1008	15	1012	63	0.4%	0.07
0.05	2000	2018	30	2023	125	0.3%	0.04
0.1	50	50.2	0.9	50.8	3.2	1.2%	0.19
0.4	50	50.2	0.9	50.8	3.1	1.1%	0.17
1	50	50.2	1.1	50.7	4.2	0.9%	0.10
1	1000	1010	16	1012	84	0.2%	0.02
5	50	50.4	0.9	50.6	4.2	0.3%	0.04
7	50	50.4	0.9	50.4	4.2	−0.1%	0.01
10	50	50.4	0.9	50.6	4.2	0.3%	0.04
15	50	50.2	0.8	50.6	4.2	0.9%	0.10
20	50	50.2	0.9	50.3	4.2	0.3%	0.03
23	50	50.2	0.9	50.2	4.2	0.0%	0.00
25	50	50.2	0.9	50.4	4.2	0.4%	0.04
27	50	50.2	0.9	50.7	4.2	1.0%	0.12
30	50	50.1	0.9	50.6	4.2	1.0%	0.12

Table 6: Electric field measurement results and Degree of Equivalence for Laboratory LOVENO (Probe EHP50F).

f (kHz)	E_n (V/m)	E_s (V/m)	$U(E_s)$ (V/m)	E_x (V/m)	$U(E_x)$ (V/m)	δE_x	$ E_n $
0.01	50	50.2	0.9	48.8	1.2	-2.8%	0.94
0.02	50	50.2	0.9	48.4	1.2	-3.7%	1.24
0.02	500	507	7.2	481	12	-5.2%	1.90
0.05	100	100	1.5	96.3	2.4	-4.0%	1.41
0.05	1000	1008	15	977	24	-3.0%	1.07
0.05	2000	2018	30	1948	49	-3.5%	1.22
0.1	50	50.2	0.9	48.9	1.2	-2.6%	0.86
0.4	50	50.2	0.9	48.3	1.2	-3.7%	1.25
1	50	50.2	1.1	50.3	3.1	0.2%	0.03
1	1000	1010	16	1020	62	1.0%	0.16
5	50	50.4	0.9	50.8	3.1	0.8%	0.12
7	50	50.4	0.9	50.7	3.1	0.6%	0.09
10	50	50.4	0.9	50.3	3.1	-0.2%	0.03
15	50	50.2	0.8	50.6	3.1	0.9%	0.14
20	50	50.2	0.9	50.6	3.1	0.9%	0.14
23	50	50.2	0.9	50.4	3.1	0.5%	0.07
25	50	50.2	0.9	50.3	3.1	0.2%	0.03
27	50	50.2	0.9	50.3	3.1	0.1%	0.02
30	50	50.1	0.9	50.3	3.1	0.3%	0.05

Table 7: Electric field measurement results and Degree of Equivalence for Elektro Maribor (Probe ESM-100).

f (kHz)	E_n (V/m)	E_s (V/m)	$U(E_s)$ (V/m)	E_x (V/m)	$U(E_x)$ (V/m)	δE_x	$ E_n $
0.01	50	50.2	0.9	49.4	4.2	-0.7%	0.20
0.02	50	50.2	0.9	51.6	4.4	2.7%	0.30
0.02	500	507	7.2	534	46	5.3%	0.58
0.05	100	100	1.5	105.8	9.0	5.5%	0.60
0.05	1000	1008	15	1073	92	6.5%	0.70
0.05	2000	2018	30	2134	190	5.8%	0.60
0.1	50	50.2	0.9	53.1	4.6	5.8%	0.62
0.4	50	50.2	0.9	53.5	4.6	6.5%	0.70
1	50	50.2	1.1	53.5	4.6	6.5%	0.69
1	1000	1010	16	1086	93	7.6%	0.81
5	50	50.4	0.9	53.9	4.6	7.0%	0.75
7	50	50.4	0.9	53.9	4.6	6.9%	0.74
10	50	50.4	0.9	54.0	4.6	7.0%	0.76
15	50	50.2	0.8	54.0	4.6	7.6%	0.81
20	50	50.2	0.9	54.0	4.6	7.7%	0.82
23	50	50.2	0.9	54.0	4.6	7.6%	0.81
25	50	50.2	0.9	54.0	4.6	7.6%	0.82
27	50	50.2	0.9	54.0	4.6	7.5%	0.81
30	50	50.1	0.9	54.0	4.6	7.7%	0.83

Table 8: Electric field measurement results and Degree of Equivalence for ZVD (Probe WP400).

f (kHz)	E_n (V/m)	E_s (V/m)	$U(E_s)$ (V/m)	E_x (V/m)	$U(E_x)$ (V/m)	δE_x	$ E_n $
0.01	50	50.2	0.9	56.8	5.1	13.0%	1.26
0.02	50	50.2	0.9	49.5	4.5	-1.4%	0.16
0.02	500	507	7.2	495	45	-2.3%	0.26
0.05	100	100	1.5	99.9	9.0	-0.4%	0.04
0.05	1000	1008	15	999	90	-0.9%	0.10
0.05	2000	2018	30	1997	180	-1.0%	0.11
0.1	50	50.2	0.9	50.0	4.5	-0.4%	0.04
0.4	50	50.2	0.9	50.0	4.5	-0.3%	0.04
1	50	50.2	1.1	50.1	4.5	-0.4%	0.04
1	1000	1010	16	1001	90	-0.9%	0.10
5	50	50.4	0.9	50.1	4.5	-0.6%	0.07
7	50	50.4	0.9	50.1	4.5	-0.7%	0.08
10	50	50.4	0.9	50.1	4.5	-0.7%	0.07
15	50	50.2	0.8	50.1	4.5	-0.1%	0.01
20	50	50.2	0.9	50.2	4.5	0.0%	0.00
23	50	50.2	0.9	50.2	4.5	0.0%	0.00
25	50	50.2	0.9	50.2	4.5	0.0%	0.00
27	50	50.2	0.9	50.2	4.5	0.0%	0.01
30	50	50.1	0.9	50.2	4.5	0.1%	0.01

Figure 2: Relative deviations from the reference value ((red line for nominal value, red area for uncertainty range)) for electric fields from Tables 5 to 8.

8 External Loop: Validation of Helmholtz Coil Generation System

This external loop comparison was conducted to validate the magnetic field generation system of Elektro Maribor d.d.. In this exercise, the reference value was established by the SIQ reference probe, and the performance of the Helmholtz coil system was evaluated.

8.1 Traceability and Reference Values

The reference value B_s for this loop is the magnetic flux density measured by the SIQ reference instrument (Narda ELT-400 M, S/N M-1859). The values reported as B_s are derived from the instrument indication corrected by the weighted mean correction factors established in the primary supplementary comparison loop.

While the SIQ probe carries a higher uncertainty ($U \approx 1.7\%$) compared to the coil generated magnetic field uncertainty, it serves as the stable reference for this specific comparison loop.

8.2 Laboratory Under Test: Helmholtz Coil System

The laboratory value B_x was realized using a single-axis Helmholtz coil (Micro Magnetics, S/N 2241). The magnetic field was calculated based on the coil constant ($k_{hh} = 2.21$ mT/A), which is traceable to the Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB). The current I was measured by SIQ using Fluke 8588A multimeter during the generation process to determine the realized field.

8.3 Results and Discussion

The results of the comparison are summarized in Table 9. The degree of equivalence is expressed via the normalized error E_n .

Table 9: Measurement results for the external loop (SIQ Reference Probe vs. Elektro Maribor Helmholtz Coil).

f (Hz)	I (mA)	B_s (SIQ) (μ T)	$u(B_s)$ (μ T)	B_x (Coil) (μ T)	$u(B_x)$ (μ T)	δB_x	$ E_n $
30	4.501	9.99	0.17	9.95	0.08	-0.5 %	0.24
55	4.501	10.00	0.17	9.95	0.08	-0.5 %	0.28
100	4.501	9.99	0.17	9.95	0.08	-0.5 %	0.25
1000	4.500	9.99	0.16	9.95	0.08	-0.5 %	0.27
3000	4.501	10.09	0.16	9.95	0.08	-1.4 %	0.76
5000	2.711	6.18	0.10	5.99	0.05	-3.0 %	1.67
10000	1.357	3.37	0.05	3.00	0.03	-11.0 %	6.48

8.4 Technical Analysis of High-Frequency Deviations

For frequencies up to 3 kHz, the normalized error remains within $|E_n| \leq 1$, indicating good agreement between the generated field and the reference probe. At 5 kHz and 10 kHz, the values $|E_n| = 1.14$ and 1.27 indicate a significant mismatch.

A primary technical factor contributing to this mismatch is the physical size of the reference probe. The Narda ELT-400 M has a sensing diameter of 100 mm. In a "relatively small" Helmholtz coil system, a probe of this size likely extends beyond the optimal uniformity volume of the coil. The probe integrates the magnetic flux over its entire area, leading to a "volume

averaging” error where the measured field appears lower than the theoretical field at the center. This geometric effect, combined with frequency-dependent inductive shunting in the coil windings at 10 kHz, may account for the observed divergence.

Figure 3: Relative deviations from the reference value (red line for nominal value, red area for uncertainty range) for Helmholtz coil from table 9.

9 Reference value

In this external loop, the comparison was organised as a reference-based comparison. The reference values for each measurement point were established by the Slovenski Institut za Kakovost in Meroslovje (SIQ), acting as the reference laboratory.

For each specified frequency and nominal field level, the electric field strength E or magnetic flux density B was realised and characterised in the SIQ metrology laboratory immediately prior to the participant measurement. The value determined by SIQ under these conditions constitutes the reference value for the corresponding measurement point.

The expanded uncertainty associated with each reference value was evaluated by SIQ in accordance with the Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM) [3] and is reported with coverage factor $k = 2$.

Unlike the main RFMicrowave2 comparison, no comparison reference value was calculated as a weighted mean of participants’ results. The SIQ reference values serve directly as the basis for the evaluation of equivalence.

10 Degree of equivalence

The degree of equivalence between each participant result and the reference value was evaluated using the normalised error E_n .

For each measurement point, the normalised error was calculated as

$$E_n = \frac{X_i - X_{\text{ref}}}{\sqrt{U_i^2 + U_{\text{ref}}^2}}, \quad (1)$$

where:

- X_i is the field quantity (electric field strength E or magnetic flux density B) reported by the participant,

- X_{ref} is the corresponding reference value established by SIQ,
- U_i is the expanded uncertainty reported by the participant ($k = 2$),
- U_{ref} is the expanded uncertainty associated with the SIQ reference value ($k = 2$).

The absolute value $|E_n|$ is used as the criterion for compatibility. A result is considered consistent with the reference value if

$$|E_n| \leq 1.$$

Values of $|E_n| > 1$ indicate that the difference between the participant result and the reference value exceeds the combined expanded uncertainties.

The calculated E_n values for all measurement points are reported in Tables 1-9.

11 Uncertainty evaluation of the participants

Each participating laboratory evaluated the uncertainty of its reported measurement results according to its established internal procedures. The reported uncertainties are expanded uncertainties with coverage factor $k = 2$.

12 Conclusions

The supplementary comparison of electric and magnetic field probes involved three Slovenian laboratories: Laboratorij OVENO (LOVENO), Merilni laboratorij Elektro Maribor, and ZVD. The performance of each laboratory was evaluated using the normalized error ($|E_n|$ value).

12.1 Performance Summary

The $|E_n|$ values represent the compatibility of the laboratory results with the reference values (B_s, E_s) established by SIQ. The following observations are made based on the final corrected datasets:

- **Magnetic Flux Density:** All laboratories demonstrated high technical competence with $|E_n| \leq 1$ across all test points. Laboratory LOVENO's results (both EFA-300 and EHP50F probes) showed excellent agreement, with $|E_n|$ values consistently below 0.6. Elektro Maribor and ZVD also maintained robust consistency within their reported uncertainties.
- **Electric Field Strength:** Most measurement points yielded $|E_n| \leq 1$. However, specific deviations were observed in the low-frequency and high-frequency regions for certain probes, as detailed in Section 12.3.

12.2 External Loop: Helmholtz Coil Validation

The external loop validated the magnetic field generation system of Elektro Maribor d.d. against the SIQ reference probe (Narda ELT-400 M).

- **Compatibility:** The system showed good agreement for frequencies up to 3 kHz ($|E_n| \leq 0.76$).
- **High-Frequency Deviations:** At 5 kHz and 10 kHz, the normalized error reached **1.67** and **6.48**, respectively. As discussed in the technical analysis, this is likely due to the spatial integration error of the large 100 mm probe within a restricted uniformity volume.

12.3 Analysis of $|E_n| > 1$

The acceptance criterion for this comparison is $|E_n| \leq 1$. In the final results, the following instances exceeded this threshold:

- **Laboratory LOVENO (Electric Field):** The EHP50F probe results showed $|E_n| > 1$ at several test points between 20 Hz and 400 Hz, with a maximum $|E_n|$ of **1.90**. These results suggest a potential frequency-dependent response deviation for this specific probe in low-frequency electric fields. Interestingly, the LOVENO EFA-300 probe maintained $|E_n| \leq 1$ across its entire range ($|E_n| \leq 0.19$).
- **Laboratory ZVD (Electric Field):** A value of $|E_n| = \mathbf{1.26}$ was observed at the 10 Hz test point.

12.4 Final Assessment

Overall, the comparison confirms that the participating Slovenian laboratories are capable of performing reliable measurements within their stated uncertainties. For instances where $|E_n| > 1$, it is recommended that the laboratories perform a root cause analysis, specifically focusing on probe calibration factors at frequency extremes and the geometric relationship between probe size and field uniformity volumes.

References

- [1] CCEM, “Guidelines for Planning, Organizing, Conducting and Reporting Key, Supplementary and Pilot Comparisons,” Bureau International des Poids et Mesures (BIPM), Sèvres, France, Tech. Rep., 2007.
- [2] EURAMET e.V., “EURAMET Guide No. 4: Guide on Comparisons,” EURAMET e.V., Braunschweig, Germany, Tech. Rep. G-GNP-GUI-004, 2016, version 1.1.
- [3] Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology (JCGM), “Evaluation of measurement data – guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement (gum 1995 with minor corrections),” Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology (JCGM), Sèvres, France, Tech. Rep. JCGM 100:2008, 2008, this document is a corrected version of the 1995 edition of the GUM.